

A systematic and synonymic list of the Pieridae of Western Palearctic butterflies hyperlinked to the original descriptions (Lepidoptera, Papilionoidea)

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Abstract

A systematic and synonymic list of the Pieridae butterflies of the Western Palearctic is presented, with all names hyperlinked to their original descriptions. The work covers taxonomic hierarchy from family to species level, incorporating historical synonyms, typification details, and bibliographic references, providing a comprehensive and navigable tool for lepidopterists and taxonomists.

Key words

Pieridae — Papilionoidea — Lepidoptera — Western Palearctic — taxonomy — nomenclature — synonymy — systematic catalogue — type species — original descriptions — type locality — butterfly classification — historical entomology.

Introduction

The family Pieridae includes species whose pale or vivid coloration has long attracted the attention of both scientists and collectors. The genus *Colias* offers a striking example, comprising highly colourful species that are especially prized by butterfly enthusiasts.

Pieridae also includes groups of species whose identification can sometimes be very difficult (for example, within the *Pontia daplidice/edusa* complex), or even impossible without recourse to genetic analyses.

Phylogenetic studies have consequently led to the splitting of several well-established species into multiple previously unrecognized entities. A well-known example is the division of *Leptidea sinapis* into three distinct species, *L. sinapis*, *L. juvernica*, and *L. reali* (Dincă *et al.* 2011). Examination of the genitalia allows *sinapis* to be separated from *juvernica* and *reali*, but it is ineffective for distinguishing between the latter two.

Phylogenetic studies have also led to taxonomic revisions among species associated with the Macaronesian fauna. Owing to the geographical isolation of several populations on individual islands, divergences in their genetic characters have in some cases been considered sufficient to recognize them as distinct species. As a result, the genera *Gonepteryx* (including *cleobule*, *palmae*, and *maderensis*), *Pieris* (with *wollastoni* and *cheiranthi*), and *Euchloe* (with *hesperidum*, *grancanariensis*, and *eversi*) have each seen an increase in the number of recognized species.

Despite these advances, several species groups continue to present substantial taxonomic difficulties, and the status of some taxa remains uncertain, whether they should be regarded as distinct species, subspecies, or evolutionary significant units (ESUs). This uncertainty applies, for example, to taxa such as *Gonepteryx eversi*, *Euchloe pechi*, and *Zegris meridionalis*.

Finally, the *Pieris napi/bryoniae/adalwinda/maura/segonzaci/balcana* complex is treated in this synonymic list according to the conclusions of Dapporto *et al.* (2022). All these taxa, whose habitus can sometimes be very distinctive, are undoubtedly closely related, and some occur in sympatry or parapatry. Multivoltinism further complicates identification, as different seasonal forms may occur and can sometimes be very similar.

All these cases are discussed in detail in [Taymans & Cuvelier \(2025\)](#).

Regular updates to a comprehensive systematic and synonymic reference list are therefore essential. A dynamic, continuously maintained list offers clear advantages over fixed, paper-based publications, which cannot be revised once issued and may become outdated relatively quickly as new taxonomic insights emerge.

Family

Pieridae Duponchel, [1835]

- [RJ] Pierides Duponchel, [1835]. In Godart, Hist. nat. Lépid. Fr.Suppl. 1(25): [381-382](#).
TG: *Pieris* Schrank, 1801.
- [ND] Pieridae Swainson, 1821. Zool. Illustr. (1)1: [[unnumbered, pl. 15](#)].
TG: *Pieris* Schrank, 1801 ; nomen nudum?
- [ND] Pieresinae Swainson, 1831. Zool. Illustr. (2)2: [[unnumbered, pl. 74](#)].
TG: *Pieris* Schrank, 1801 ; nomen nudum?
- [RJ] Pieridina Herrich-Schäffer, 1853. Samml. Neu. Aussereur. Schmett.: [54](#).
TG: *Pieris* Schrank, 1801.
- [RJ] Pierididae Reuter, [1896]. Acta Soc. Sc. Fenn. 22(1): [228](#).
TG: *Pieris* Schrank, 1801.
- [ICZN] Pieridae Duponchel, [1835]. Opinion 500 (ICZN, 1958. Opin. Declar. Int. Comm. Zool. Nomencl. 17(22): [395-422](#)).
TG: *Pieris* Schrank, 1801.
- [JS] Ascidae Hampson, 1918. Novit. Zool. 25(2): [385](#), [388](#).
TG: *Ascia* Scopoli, 1777.
- [JS] Futuronervidae Bryk, 1928. Entomol. Z. 42(5): [49-50](#).
TG: *Futuronerva* Bryk, 1928 ; anecdotal name.

Subfamily

Dismorphiinae Schatz, 1886

- [ORIG] Dismorphiden Schatz, [1886]. In: Staudinger & Schatz, Exot. Schmett. 2(2): [56-58, pl. 4](#).
TG: *Dismorphia* Hübner, [1816].
- [JH] Dismorphina Godman & Salvin, [1889]. Biol. Centr.-Amer. Ins. Lep.-Rhop. 2: [173](#).
TG: *Dismorphia* Hübner, [1816].
- [JH] Dismorphinae Kirby, 1896. Hand-Book Order Lep. (1)2: [177](#).
TG: *Dismorphia* Hübner, [1816].
- [JH] Dismorphiadae Grote, 1900. Proc. amer. phil. Soc. 39: [12-13](#).
TG: *Dismorphia* Hübner, [1816].

Tribe

Leptideini Grote, 1897

- [ORIG] Leptidiinae Grote, 1897. Mitth. Roemer-Museum Hildesh. 8: [14](#).
TG: *Leptidea* Billberg, 1820.
- [JS] Leptideidi Verity, 1947. Farfalle diurne Italia 3: [114](#).
TG: *Leptidea* Billberg, 1820.
- [ND] Leptosiidi Wheeler, 1903. Butt. Switzerl. Alps: [65](#).
TG: *Leptosia* Hübner, [1818]

Genus

Leptidea Billberg, 1820

- [ORIG] *Leptidea* Billberg, 1820. Enum. Ins. Mus. Billb.: [76](#).
TS: *Papilio sinapis* Linnaeus, 1758 by monotypy.
- [RJ] *Leucophasia* Stephens, 1827. Illust. Brit. Entomol. 1: [24-25](#).
TS: *Papilio sinapis* Linnaeus, 1758 by monotypy.
- [JS] *Azalais* Grote, 1900. Proc. amer. phil. Soc. 39: [13](#).
TS: *Leucophasia gigantea* Leech, 1890 by original designation.

Leptidea duponcheli (Staudinger, 1871)

- [ORIG] *Leucophasia duponcheli* Staudinger, 1871. Catal. Lepid. eur. Faunengeb. 1: [5](#).
TL: S France.
- [JH] *Pieris lathyri* Duponchel, 1834. In: Godart, Hist. Nat. Lépid. France Suppl. 1: [274-275](#), [pl. 43](#), [fig. 4-5](#), [325](#).
TL: Aix-en-Provence (S France) ; *nec Leptosia lathyri* Hübner, [1819]. Verz. bekannt. Schmett.: [95](#).
- [JH] *Leptidia* [sic] *duponcheli lorkovici* Pfeiffer, 1932. In: Osthelder & Pfeiffer, Mitt. Münch. Entomol. Ges. 22: [20](#).
TL: Marasch (Turkey).
- [JS] *Leptidea duponcheli* race *fragilis* Verity, 1937. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 49(Suppl.): [10-11](#).
TL: Thessaloniki (N Greece).
- [JS] *Leptidea duponcheli* ssp. *majae* Alberti, 1969. Dt. Entomol. Z. (NF)16: [191-192](#), [pl. 1](#), [fig. 1a-b.-2a-b](#).
TL: Kislovodsk (N Caucasus, Russian Federation).

Leptidea morsei (Fenton, 1882)

- [ORIG] *Leucophasia morsei* Fenton, 1882. In: Ishikawa, *Papilio* 2(3): [35-36](#), [fig.](#)
TL: Hokkaidō Isl. (Japan).
- [JH] *Leptosia morsei* Fenton, [1882]. Proc. Sci. Zool. Soc. London 1881: [855](#).
TL: Iburi, Hokkaidō Isl. (Japan)
- [IFS] *Leptidia* [sic] *sinapis* ab. *major* Grund, 1905. Entomol. Z. 19(26): [145-146](#), [fig. 4-7](#).
TL: Agrams (Croatia).
- [IFS] *Leptidia* [sic] *sinapis* ab. *croatica* Grund, 1905. Entomol. Z. 19(26): [146-147](#), [fig. 11-16](#).
TL: Agrams (Croatia).
- [JS] *Leptosia sinapis* race *acuta* Verity, 1922. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 34(5): [90](#).
TL: Austria.
- [SN] *Leptosia sinapis* race *major* Verity, 1922. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 34(5): [90](#).
Stat. nov. for *Leptidia* [sic] *sinapis* ab. *major* Grund, 1905.

Leptidea juvernica Williams, 1946

- [ORIG] *Leptidea sinapis* ssp. *juvernica* Williams, 1946. Entomologist 79(992): [1-3](#).
TL: Kildare (Leinster prov., W Ireland).
- [JS] *Leptidea reali* ssp. *melanogyna* Lorković, 1993. Natura Croatica 2(1): [21-22](#), [fig. 25-28](#), [19-22](#).
TL: Kanal, Maksimir (Zagreb, Croatia).

[JS] *Leptidea reali* ssp. *jonvillei* Mazel, 2000. Linn. Belg. 17(7): [283-284](#).
TL: Fontaine Froide, Viremont (Jura dep., E France).

Leptidea sinapis (Linnaeus, 1758)

[ORIG] *Papilio sinapis* Linnaeus, 1758. Syst. Nat. (ed. 10)1: [468](#).

TL: Sweden.

[JH] *Papilio candidus* Retzius, 1783. Gen. Spec. Ins.: [30](#).

TL: - ; nec *Papilio candida* Cramer, [1780]: [82](#).

[JS] *Papilio erysimi* Borkhausen, 1788. Naturg. eur. Schmett.1: [132-133](#).

TL: Germany.

[RJ] *Leptosia lathyri* Hübner, [1819]. Verz. bekannt. Schmett.: [95](#).

TL: -.

[JS] *Leucophasia loti* Rennie, 1832. Consp. Brit. Butt. Moths: [4-5](#).

TL: Kent, Surrey,... (UK).

[JS] *Leucophasia sinapis* var. *diniensis* Boisduval, 1840. Gen. Ind. Meth. Eur. Lepid.: [6](#).

TL: Digne (S France).

[JS] *Leucophasia umbratica* Trimoulet, 1858. Actes Soc. Linn. Bordeaux 22: [12](#).

TL: Pessac (Gironde dep., SW France).

[JS] *Leucophasia sinapis* var. *sartha* Rühl, 1893. In: Heyne, Pal. Grossschmett.: [143](#).

TL: S Europe, Asia Minor.

[IFS] *Leptidea sinapis sinapis deserticola* Verity, [1908]. Rhopal. Pal.: 202.

TL: Shar Deresy (Syria).

[JS] *Leptidea sinapis* var. *syriaca* Culot, 1909. Bull. Soc. Lépid. Genève1(3): 248.

TL: Syria.

[JS] *Leptidea sinapis* race *corsica* Verity, [1911]. Rhopal. Pal.: 343.

TL: Corsica (S France).

[JS] *Leptidea sinapis* race *majorides* Verity, [1911]. Rhopal. Pal.: 344.

TL: Kiev (Ukraine).

[JS] *Leptidea (Leucophasia) sinapis* ssp. *stabiaram* Stauder, 1914. Z. Wiss. Insektbiol. 10: [371, pl. 2, fig. 5-6](#).

TL: Monte Faito (Campania, Italy).

[JS] *Leptidea sinapis* f. *obscurata* Verity, 1916. Bull. Soc. Entomol. Ital. 48: [182](#).

TL: Elba Isl. (Italy).

[JS] *Leptidea sinapis* f. *transiens* Verity, 1916. Entomol. Rec. J. Var.28(5): [98](#).

TL: New Forest (UK).

[JS] *Leptidea sinapis* f. *bivittata* Verity, 1916. Entomol. Rec. J. Var.28(5): [98](#).

TL: Tuscany (Italy).

[JS] *Leptidea sinapis* race *nigrescens* Verity, 1919. Entomol. Rec. J. Var.31(5): [87](#).

TL: Arno (Italy).

[JS] *Leptidea sinapis detersa* Rocci, 1920. Atti Soc. Ligust. Sci. Nat. 30: 185.

TL: Liguria (NW Italy).

- [JS] *Leptidea sinapis lineata* Rocci, 1920. Atti Soc. Ligust. Sci. Nat. 30: 185.
TL: Liguria (NW Italy).
- [JS] *Leptiosia sinapis* race *acuta* Verity, 1922. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 34(5): [90](#).
TL: Austria.
- [SN] *Leptiosia sinapis* race *deserticola* Verity, 1922. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 34(5): [90](#).
Stat. nov. for. *Leptidea sinapis sinapis deserticola* Verity, 1908.
- [SN] *Leptosia sinapis* race *bivittata* Verity, 1922. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 34(5): [91](#).
Stat. nov. for. *Leptidea sinapis* f. *bivittata* Verity, 1917.
- [JS] *Leptosia sinapis monovittata* Verity, 1924. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 36(7-8): [111](#).
TL: Forte dei Marmi (Lucca prov., Italy).
- [JS] *Leptidea sinapis* race *pseudodiniensis* Pfeiffer, 1927. Mitt. Munch. Entomol. Ges. 17: [35-36](#).
TL: Anatolia (W Turkey).
- [JS] *Leptidea sinapis pumilia* Dannehl, 1933. Entomol. Z. 46(22): [232](#).
TL: S Maiella (C Italy).
- [JS] *Leptidea sinapis mendesi* Bryk, 1940. Arkiv Zool. 32A(22): 9.
TL: Cintra (C Portugal).
- [JS] *Leptidea sinapis* race *lathyri-cana* Verity, 1947. Farfalle diurne Italia 3: 131.
TL: Sappada (Udine prov. NE Italy).
- [JS] *Leptidea sinapis* ssp. *maitenensis* Schmidt-Koehl, 1968. Entomol. Z. 75: [227](#).
TL: TL: Granada, Sierra Nevada (S Spain).
- [JS] *Leptidea sinapis* ssp. *colladoi* Fernandez-Rubio, 1969. Alexanor 6: 13.
TL: Sierra Nevada (S Spain).
- [JS] *Leptidea sinapis* ssp. *realiformis* Mazel, 2001. Linneana Belgica 18(4): [200](#).
TL: Kildare (Ireland).

Leptidea reali Reissinger, [1990]

- [ORIG] *Leptidea sinapis reali* Reissinger, [1990]. Atalanta 20: [173](#).
Nom. nov. for *Leptidea lorkovicii* Real, 1988.
- [JH] *Leptidea lorkovicii* Real, 1988. Mém. Comm. Liais. Rech. Ecof. Jura 4: [17-24](#).
TL: La Hontailla, Nohèdes (Pyrénées-Orientales dep., S France) ; nec *Leptidia* [sic] *duponcheli lorkovici* Pfeiffer, 1932: [20](#).

Subfamily

Coliadinae Swainson, 1827

- [ND] Coliadae Swainson, 1821. Zool. Illustr. 1: [[unnumbered](#)], (pl. [22](#)).
TG: *Colias* Fabricius, 1807 ; Nomen dubium.
- [RJ] Coliana Swainson, 1827. Phil. Mag., n.s. 1(3): [188](#).
TG: *Colias* Fabricius, 1807 ; Name rejected by Direction 99 (ICZN, 1958).
- [JS] Dryaden Schatz, [1886]. In: Staudinger & Schatz, Exot. Schmett. 2(2): [66](#).
TG: *Dryas* Boisduval, [1847] (= *Eronia* Hübner, [1823]).
- [JS] Callidryinae Kirby, 1896. Hand-book Order Lepid.(1)2: [207](#).

- TG: *Callidryas* Boisduval & Le Conte, [1830] = (*Phoebis* Hübner, [1819])
[ICZN] Coliadinae Swainson, 1827.Phil. Mag.,n.s. 1(3): [188](#).
TG: *Colias* Fabricius, 1807 ; Name placed on the Official List by Direction 99 (ICZN, 1958).

Tribe

Rhodocerini Duponchel, [1835]

- [ND] Rhodocerides Duponchel, [1835]. In: Godart, Hist. nat. Lépid. suppl. 1: [385](#).
TG: *Rhodocera* Boisduval & Leconte, [1830] (= *Gonepteryx* Leach, [1815]).
[JS] Gonepterygidi Verity, 1920. Boll. Lab. Zool. Gen. Portici 14: [51](#).
TG: *Gonepteryx* [Leach], [1815].
[JS] Gonepterygini Niculescu, 1963. Faun. Rep. pop. Rom. Ins. 11(6): 183.
TG: *Gonepteryx* [Leach], [1815].

Genus

Gonepteryx Leach, 1815

- [ORIG] *Gonepteryx* Leach, 1815. In: Brewster, Edinburgh Encycl. 9: [127-128](#).
TS: *Papilio rhamni* Linnaeus, 1758 by monotypy.
[JS] *Rhodocera* Boisduval & Leconte, [1830]. Hist. Lépid. sept.: [70](#).
TS: *Papilio rhamni* Linnaeus, 1758 by subsequent designation by Blanchard, 1840. Hist. Nat. Ins. 3: [431](#).
[JS] *Earina* Speyer, 1839. *Isis* 1839(2): [98](#).
TS: *Papilio rhamni* Linnaeus, 1758 by subsequent designation by Klots, 1931. Entomol. Amer. (NS)12(3): [179](#).
[JS] *Eugonepteryx* Nekrutenko, 1968. Phyl. geogr. distr. *Gonepteryx*: 27, 57.
TS: *Papilio rhamni* Linnaeus, 1758 by subsequent designation by Kudrna, 1975. Entomol. Gaz. 26(1) : 12.
[JS] *Isogonepteryx* Nekrutenko, 1968. Phyl. geogr. distr. *Gonepteryx*: 27, 47.
TS: *Papilio cleopatra* Linnaeus, 1767by original designation.

Gonepteryx rhamni (Linnaeus, 1758)

- [ORIG] *Papilio rhamni* Linnaeus, 1758. Syst. Nat. (ed. 10)1: [470](#).
TL: Sweden.
[JS] *Papilio eclipsis* Linnaeus, 1763. Centur. Ins. Rar.: [23](#).
TL: North America [error].
[JS] *Papilio canicularis* Retzius, 1783. Gen. Spec. Ins.: [30](#).
TL: Sweden.
[JS] *Gonepteryx rhamni* f. *meridionalis* Röber, 1907. In Seitz, Gross-Schmett. Erde (1)1: [60-61](#).
TL: Algeria ; S Turkey.
[JS] *Gonepteryx rhamni* race *transiens* Verity, 1913. J. linn. Soc., Zool 32(215): [180](#).
TL: Florence (Italy).
[ND] *Gonepteryx rhamni intermedia* Verity, 1916. Bull. Soc. Entomol. Ital. 47: [51](#).
TL: Macerata (Italy) ; Nomen nudum, not described.
[JS] *Gonepteryx rhamni* race *transiens-rhamni* Verity, 1947. Farfalle diurne Italia 3: 307.

- TL: Milano ; Torino (N Italy).
 [JS] *Gonepteryx rhamni* ssp. *gravesi* Higgins, 1956. The Entomologist 89: 65.
 TL: Kildare (Ireland).
 [JS] *Gonepteryx rhamni* ssp. *matsakii* Kattulas & Koutsaftikis, 1978. Biol. Gallo-Hellen 7: 155.
 TL: Kastellorizo Isl. (Greece).
 [JS] *Gonepteryx rhamni* ssp. *atlasica* Krajcik, 2015. Animma.x 67: 4.
 TL: Ras Elm (Morocco).

Gonepteryx cleobule (Hübner, [1824])

- [ORIG] *Anteos cleobule* Hübner, [1824]. Zutr. Samml. exot. Schmett. 3: [pl. \[79\], fig. 455-456](#), [1831]: [17-18](#).
 TL: Tenerife (Canary Isl., Spain).

ESU *G. eversi* Rehnelt, 1974

- [ORIG] *Gonepteryx eversi* Rehnelt, 1974. Entomol. Z.84(5): [51-52](#).
 TL: Gomera (Canary Isl., Spain).

Gonepteryx cleopatra (Linnaeus, 1767)

- [ORIG] *Papilio cleopatra* Linnaeus, 1767. Syst. Nat. (ed. 12) 1(2): [765](#).
 TL: Algeria.
 [JS] *Rhodocera cleopatra* var. *italica* Gerhard, 1882. Berl. Entomol. Z. 26(1): [125](#).
 TL: Dalmatia (Croatia) ; Italy.
 [IFS] *Rhodocera cleopatra* var. [ab.] *virgo* Röber, 1897. Entomol. Nachr. 23(17-18): [263](#).
 TL: S Russian Federation [error].
 [JS] *Rhodocera cleopatra* var. *massiliensis* Foulquier, 1899. Cat. Rais. Lépid. Bouches-du-Rhône: 7.
 TL: Bouches-du-Rhône (S France).
 [JS] *Gonepteryx cleopatra* f.[var.] *mauretanica* Röber, 1907. In: Seitz, Gross-Schmet. Erde (1)1: 61.
 TL: Batna (NE Algeria).
 [JS] *Gonepteryx cleopatra dalmatica* Verity, [1911]. Rhop. Pal.: 286.
 TL: Dalmatia (Croatia).
 [JS] *Gonepteryx cleopatra insularis* Verity, [1911]. Rhop. Pal.: 286.
 TL: Creta (S Greece).
 [JS] *Gonepteryx cleopatra europaeus* Verity, 1913. J. Linn. Soc. Lond, Zool. 32: [180](#).
 TL: Florence (Italy).
 [JS] *Gonepteryx cleopatra pallida* Rocci, 1920. Atti Soc. Ligust. Sci. Nat. Geogr. 30(4): 203.
 TL: Genova (NW Italy).
 [JS] *Gonepteryx cleopatra balearica* Bubacek, 1920. Verh. Zool.-Bot. Ges. Wien 70: [\(85\)-\(86\)](#).
 TL: Mallorca (Balearic Islands, Spain).
 [JS] *Gonepteryx cleopatra* f.[var.] *palmata* Turati, 1922. Atti Soc. Ital. Sci. Nat. 60: [216, fig.](#)
 TL: Uadi Derna (NE Libya).
 [JS] *Gonepteryx cleopatra* f.[var.] *fiorii* Turati & Fiori, 1930. Mem. Soc. Entomol. Ital. 9: [199](#).

TL: S. Isidoro (Rhodes, SE Greece).

[JS] *Gonepteryx cleopatra* var. *bicolorata* Chnéour, 1948. Bull. Soic. Hist. Nat. Afr. n. 38(1-9): [22](#).

TL: Tunisia.

[JS] *Gonepteryx cleopatra* var. *rosei* Gross, 1973. Entomol. Z. 83: 161.

TL: Las Mercedes (Tenerife, Canary Isl., Spain).

[JS] *Gonepteryx cleopatra* ssp. *petronella* Freina, 1977. Atalanta 8: 273.

TL: Ibiza (Balearic Islands, Spain).

Gonepteryx palmae Stamm, 1963

[ORIG] *Gonepteryx cleopatra* ssp. *palmae* Stamm, 1963. Entomol. Z. 73(6): [49-50, fig. 5](#).

TL: La Palma (Canary Isl., Spain).

Gonepteryx maderensis C. Felder, 1862

[ORIG] *Gonepteryx* [sic] *cleopatra* var. *maderensis* Felder C., 1862. Verh. zool.-bot. Ges. Wien 12: [473](#).

TL: Madeira (Portugal).

Gonepteryx farinosa (Zeller, 1847)

[ORIG] *Rhodocera farinosa* Zeller, 1847. Isis von Oken 1847(1): [5-6](#).

TL: Fethiye (Aegean reg., Turkey).

Tribe

Coliadini Swainson, 1827

[ND] Coliadae Swainson, 1821. Zool. Illustr. 1: [\[unnumbered\]](#), (pl. [22](#)).

TG: *Colias* Fabricius, 1807 ; *Nomen dubium*.

[RJ] Coliana Swainson, 1827.Phil. Mag.,n.s. 1(3): [188](#).

TG: *Colias* Fabricius, 1807

[JS] Callidryinae Kirby, 1896. Hand-book Order Lepid.(1)2: [207](#).

TG: *Callidryas* Boisduval & Le Conte, [1830] =(*Phoebis* Hübner, [1819])

[ICZN] Coliana Swainson, 1827.Phil. Mag.,n.s. 1(3): [188](#).

TG: *Colias* Fabricius, 1807 ; Name placed on the Official List by Direction 99 (ICZN, 1958).

Genus

Catopsilia Hübner, [1819]

[ORIG] *Catopsilia* Hübner, [1819]. Verz. bekannt. Schmett. (7): [98](#).

TS: *Papilo crocale* Cramer, 1775 by subsequent designation by Scudder, 1872: [58](#).

[JS] *Murtia* Hübner, [1819]. Verz. bekannt. Schmett. (7): [98](#).

TS: *Mancipium minna* Hübner, [1809]. Samml. Exot. Schmett. 1: pl. [144](#) by monotypy.

Catopsilia florella (Fabricius, 1775)

[ORIG] *Papilio florella* Fabricius, 1775. Syst. entomol.: [479](#).

TL: Sierra Leone.

Genus

Colias Fabricius, 1807

- [ORIG] *Colias* Fabricius, 1807. In: Illiger, Mag. Insektenk.6: [284](#).
TS: *Papilio hyale* Linnaeus, 1758 by designation by Opinion 146 (ICZN, 1943: [111](#)).
- [JH] *Colias* subgenus *Eurymus* Horsfield, [1829]. Cat. lepid. Ins. Mus. East-India: [134](#).
TS: *Papilio hyale* Linnaeus, 1758 by original designation ; *nec* Rafinesque, 1815. Analyse Nat.: [117](#).
- [ND] *Ganura* Zetterstedt, [1839]. Ins. Lapon. (4): [908](#).
TS: - ; nomen dubium, this name was published in synonymy and is unavailable (Code ICZN, Art. 11.6).
- [JS] *Scalidoneura* Butler, 1871. Proc. zool. Soc. Lond. 1871: [250-251](#).
TS: *Scalidoneura hermina* Butler, 1871 by original designation.
- [JS] *Eriocolias* Watson, 1895. Entomologist 28: [167-168](#).
TS: *Papilio edusa* Fabricius, 1787 by original designation.
- [JS] *Coliastes* Hemming, 1931. Entomologist 64: 273.
TS: *Papilio hyale* Linnaeus, 1758 by original designation.
- [JS] *Protocolias* Petersen, 1963. J. Res. Lepid. 1(2): [144](#).
TS: Type species: *Colias imperialis* Butler, 1871 by original designation.
- [JS] *Protocolias* subg. *Mesocolias* Petersen, 1963. J. Res. Lepid. 1(2): [144](#).
TS: *Colias vauthierii* Guérin-Méneville, 1830 by original designation.
- [JS] *Colias* subg. *Neocolias* Berger, 1986. Lambillionea 86(7/8, suppl.): [21](#).
TS: *Papilio erate* Esper, 1805 by original designation.
- [JS] *Colias* subg. *Palaeocolias* Berger, 1986. Lambillionea 86(7/8, suppl.): [21-22](#).
TS: *Colias ponteni* Wallengren, 1860 by original designation.
- [JS] *Colias* subg. *Euocolias* Berger, 1986. Lambillionea 86(7/8, suppl.): [22](#).
TS: *Papilio palaeno* Linnaeus, 1760 by original designation.
- [JS] *Colias* subg. *Similicolias* Berger, 1986. Lambillionea 86(7/8, suppl.): [23](#).
TS: *Papilio lesbia* Fabricius, 1775 by original designation.
- [JS] *Colias* subg. *Euriocolias* Berger, 1986. Lambillionea 86(7/8, suppl.): [23](#).
TS: *Papilio croceus* Geoffroy, 1785 by original designation.
- [JS] *Colias* subg. *Paracolias* Berger, 1986. Lambillionea 86(7/8, suppl.): [24](#).
TS: *Colias dimera* Doubleday, 1847 by original designation.
- [JS] *Asiocolias* Korb, 2005. Cat. Butt. ex-USSR: 20.
TS: *Colias christophi* Grun-Grshimailo, 1885 by original designation.

Colias palaeno (Linnaeus, 1761)

- [ORIG] *Papilio palaeno* Linnaeus, 1761. Fauna Suec. (ed. 2): [272](#).
TL: Uppsala (Sweden).
- [JH] *Papilio hyale* Hufnagel, 1766. Berlin. Mag. 2(1): [76-77](#).
TL: Berlin (Germany) ; *nec* Linnaeus, 1758. Syst. Nat. (ed. 10)1: [469](#).

- [JS] *Papilio europome* Esper, [1778]. Schmett. Abb. Nat.1(1): [367-368](#) [1779], [pl. 42, fig. 1-2](#) [1778].
TL: Saxe (Germany)
- [JS] *Papilio philomene* Hübner, [1805]. Samml. eur. Schmett.1: [pl. 117, fig. 602-603](#).
TL: - (Germany ?).
- [JS] *Colias palaeno europomene* Ochseneheimer, 1816. Schmett. Eur. 4: [156-157](#).
TL: Switzerland.
- [JS] *Colias valeria* Sievers, 1860. In: Motschulsky, Ét. Entomol. 8: [146, nota](#).
TL: St. Petersburg (Russian Federation).
- [JS] *Colias palaeno* var. *lapponica* Staudinger, 1861. Cat. Lepid. Eur.: [3](#).
TL: Lapland (Finland ; Sweden ; Murmansk obl., Russian Federation).
- [JS] *Colias palaeno* var. *cretacea* Aurivillius, 1888. Nord. Fjärilar: [6](#).
TL: Lapland (Finland).
- [JS] *Colias palaeno* var. *caflischi* Caradja, 1893. Soc. Entomol. 8(4): [26-27](#).
TL: Grisons (Switzerland).
- [JS] *Colias palaeno* var. *alpina* Spuler, 1901. Schmett. Eur. 1: [9](#).
TL: Alps.
- [JS] *Colias palaeno* var. *synonyma* Bryk, 1923. Entomol. Tidskr. 44(2): [108](#).
TL: C Sweden.
- [JS] *Colias palaeno* f. *de-prunneri* Rocca, 1944. Mem. Soc. Entomol. Ital. 23: [21](#).
TL: Colle del Piccolo Moncenisio (Savoie dep., SE France ; Piedmont, NW Italy).
- [JS] *Colias palaeno* ssp. *pruefferi* Krzywicki, 1967. Ann. zool., Warsz.25(1): 106-108, 137-140, pl. 1, fig. 2-3, pl. 2, fig. 6-10.
TL: Białowieżaer Urwald (Poland).

Colias tyche (Boeber, 1812)

- [ORIG] *Papilio tyche* Boeber, 1812. Mém. Soc. Nat. Mosc. 3: [21](#), pl. 1, fig. 3-4.
TL: Siberia (Russian Federation).
- [JS] *Colias werdandi* Zetterstedt, [1839]. Ins. Lappon.: [908](#).
TL: Norway.

Colias hecla Lefebvre, 1836

- [ORIG] *Colias hecla* Lefebvre, 1836. Ann. Soc. entomol. Fr. 5: [383-387, pl. 9](#).
TL: Groenland.
- [JS] *Colias hecla* var. *sulitelma* Aurivillius, 1890. Bih. Kongl. Svenska Vet.-Akad. Handl. 15(4)(1): [11-12](#).
TL: Sulitjelma Mt. (Norway ; Sweden).

Colias phicomone (Esper, [1780])

- [ORIG] *Papilio phicomone* Esper, [1780]. Schmett. Abb. Nat. 1(2): [32-33, pl. 56 \(cont. 6\), fig. 1-2](#).
TL: Styria (Austria).
- [JS] *Colias phicomone* ssp. *phila* Fruhstorfer, 1903. Dt. Entomol. Z. 16(1): [47](#).
TL: Kashmir [error, see Grieshuber *et al.*, 2012] = Alps?

- [JS] *Colias phicomone* var. *saturata* Austaut, 1905. Entomol. Z. 18(36): [143](#).
TL: Tiefenberg (Grisons, Switzerland).
- [JS] *Colias phicomone* ssp. *periphaes* Fruhstorfer, 1908. Entomol. Z. 22(12): [51](#).
TL: border Upper Austria, Salzburg and Styria (Austria).
- [JS] *Colias phicomone* f. *oberthueri* Verity, [1909]. Rhopl. Palaeart.: 231.
TL: Vernet-les-Bains (Pyrénées-Orientales dep., France).
- [JS] *Colias phicomone* race *pulverulenta* Verity, 1926. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 38(12): [170-171](#).
TL: Oulx (Piedmont, Turin prov., NW Italy).
- [JS] *Colias phicomone* race *alpiumnitida* Verity, 1926. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 38(12): [171](#).
TL: Vallesco, Valdieri (Piedmont, Cuneo prov., NW Italy).
- [JS] *Colias phicomone* var. *juliani* Hospital, 1948. Trab. Mus. Cienc. Nat. Barc. (N.S. Zool.) 1(2): [11](#).
TL: Picos de Europa (NW Spain).

***Colias thisoa* Ménétériés, 1832**

- [ORIG] *Colias thisoa* Ménétériés, 1832. Cat. rais. Caucase: [244-245](#).
TL: Mount Shahdagh (Azerbaijan).
- [JS] *Colias helena* Herrich-Schäffer, [1844]. Syst. Bearb. Schmett. Eur. 1: [pl. 45, fig. 206-207](#) ; 6 (Nachtrag): [22-23](#) [1851].
TL: Mt. Ararat (E Turkey).
- [JS] *Colias eos* Herrich-Schäffer, [1848]. Syst. Bearb. Schmett. Eur. 1: [pl. 81, fig. 395-396](#) ; 6 (Nachtrag): [22](#) [1851].
TL: Mt. Ararat (E Turkey).
- [JS] *Colias thisoa* ssp. *strandiana* Sheljuzhko, 1935. Folia Zool. Hydrobiol. 8(1): [138](#).
TL: Mt. Aragats (W Armenia).

***Colias chrysotheme* (Esper, [1781])**

- [ORIG] *Papilio chrysotheme* Esper, [1781]. Schmett. Abb. Nat. 1(2): [89-90, pl. 65 \(cont. 15\), fig. 3-4](#).
TL: Kremnica (Slovakia).
- [JS] *Colias chrysotheme* var. *schugurowi* Verity, 1908. Rhopl. Palaeart.: pl. 47, fig. 18-19.
TL: Malmish, Viatka gov. (Russian Federation).
- [JS] *Colias chrysotheme* ssp. *ksienzhopolskii* Obratzsov, 1936. Folia zool. Hydrobiol. 9(1): 43-44.
TL: Vessjolaja Bokovenjka Park (Kirovohrad obl., Ukraine).
- [JS] *Colias chrysotheme* ssp. *praealpina* Kovács, 1956. Ann. Hist.-Nat. Mus. Natn. Hung. 48: [430](#).
TL: Magyaróvár (=Mosonmagyaróvár, NW Hungary).

***Colias erate* (Esper, [1805])**

- [ORIG] *Papilio erate* Esper, [1805]. Schmett. Abb. Nat. Suppl. 2: [13-14, pl. 119 \(cont. 74\), fig. 3](#).
TL: Sarepta, Volgograd oblast (Russian Federation).
- [JS] *Colias neriene* Fischer de Waldheim, 1823. Entomogr. Russ. 2: [251, pl. 11, fig. 3-4](#).
TL: Sarepta, Volgograd oblast (Russian Federation).
- [JS] *Colias nereine chrysozona* Boisduval, 1840. Gen. Index Method. Eur. Lepid.: [7](#).
TL: Taganrog (Rostov obl., Russian Federation).

- [JS] *Colias helichtha* Lederer, 1853. Verh. Zool.-Bot. Ver. Wien 2(Abhandl): [18, 33, pl. 2, fig. 3-4](#).
TL: - (=Sarepta, Volgograd oblast, Russian Federation).
- [JS] *Colias erate* var. *beckeri* Gerhard, 1882. Berl. Entomol. Z. 26(1): [125](#).
TL: Sarepta, Volgograd oblast (Russian Federation).
- [IFS] *Colias erate* ab. *edusoides* Krulikovsky, 1903. Rev. Russe Entomol. 3: [301](#).
TL: - ; hybrid *Colias erate* Esper x *Colias edusa* Fabricius.
- [JS] *Colias erate* f. *edusoides* Verity, 1908. Rhopl. Palaearct.: 219.
TL: Poltava (Russian Federation)
- [NN] *Colias erate besignata* Sheljuzhko, 1913. Dt. Entomol. Z. 27(1): [20](#).
Nom. nov. for *C. erate edusoides* Verity ; *nec* Krulikovsky, 1903. Rev. Russe Entomol. 3: 301.

Colias croceus (Geoffroy, 1785)

- [ORIG] *Papilio croceus* Geoffroy, 1785. In: Fourcroy, Entomol. Paris. 2 : [250](#).
TL: Paris (France).
- [JH] *Papilio hyale* [Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775. Ank. syst. Werkes Schmett. Wienerg.: [165](#).
TL: Vienna (Austria) ; *nec* Linnaeus, 1758. Syst. Nat. (ed. 10)1: [469](#).
- [JH] *Papilio edusa* Fabricius, 1787. Mantissa Insect. 2: [23](#).
TL: Spain ; *nec* Fabricius, 1777. Gen. Ins.: [255-256](#).
- [JH] *Papilio electra* Lewin, 1795. Pap. Gr. Brit.: [68-69, pl. 32, fig. 1-3](#).
TL: - (Great Britain, UK) ; *nec* Linnaeus, 1767. Syst. Nat. (ed. 12) 1(2): [764](#).
- [JH] *Papilio helice* Hübner, [1800]. Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 87, fig. 440-441](#).
TL: - (Germany ?) ; *nec* Linnaeus, 1764. Mus. Lud. Ulr.: [243](#).
- [JS] *Colias edusa* var. *pyrenaica* Grum-Grshimailo, 1893. Horae Soc. Entomol. Ross. 27(3/4): [383](#).
TL: Pyrenees (France ; Spain).
- [JS] *Colias croceus* race *ampla* Verity, 1919. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. [31(5): [87](#)]; 31(7), [121](#) , correction.
TL: S. Martino, Palermo (Sicily, S Italy).
- [JS] *Colias croceus* race *croceoviridis* Berger, 1936. Lambillionea 36(8/9): 200.
TL: Majkop (Adygea Rep., Russian Federation).

Colias hyale (Linnaeus, 1758)

- [ORIG] *Papilio hyale* Linnaeus C. 1758. Syst. Nat. (ed. 10)1: [469](#).
TL: Essex and Canterbury (UK).
- [JH] *Papilio palaeno* [Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775. Ank. syst. Werkes Schmett. Wienerg.: [165](#).
TL: Vienna (Austria) ; *nec* Linnaeus, 1761. Fauna Suec. (ed. 2): [272](#).
- [JS] *Colias hyale* var. *hyalis* Kirby, 1858. List. Br. Rhopal.: [1].
TL: UK.
- [JS] *Colias hyale* var. *kirbyi* Lewis, 1872. Disc. Law Prior. Entomol. Nomencl.: [34](#).
TL: UK.
- [JS] *Colias hyale* var. *uhli* Kováts, 1899. Entomol. Z. 12(22): [169-170](#).
TL: Budapest (Hungary).

Colias alfacariensis Ribbe, 1905

- [ORIG] *Colias hyale* ab. *alfacariensis* Ribbe, 1905. Societas entomol. 20(18): [137](#).
TL: Sierra de Alfacar (Granada prov., S Spain) ; placed on the Official List of Specific Names in Zoology by Opinion 1657 (ICZN, 1991).
- [JH] *Colias hyale* var. *sareptensis* Alphéraky, 1875. Trudy Russk. Entomol. Obshch 8(2): [153-154](#).
TL: Taranrog, Sarepta (S Russian Federation) ; ? *nec* Staudinger, 1871. Cat. Lepid. Eur. : [5](#).
- [SS] *Colias hyale* var. *alba* Rühl, 1892. Pal. Grossschmett. Naturg. 1: [156](#).
TL: Nischapur (NE Iran).
- [NN] *Colias hyale* var. *meridionalis* Krulikowsky, 1903. Rev. Russe Entomol. 3(5): [301-302](#), *nota*.
Nom. nov. for *Colias hyale sareptensis* Alphéraky, 1875.
- [JS] *Colias hyale hyale* race *australis* Verity, [1911]. Rhopl. Palaearct.: 347.
TL: Andalusia (S Spain) ; availability of specific names confirmed by Opinion 1657 (ICZN, 1991).
- [JS] *Colias hyale* f. *calida* Verity, 1916. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 28(5): [99](#).
TL: Tuscany (Italy) ; availability of specific names confirmed by Opinion 1657 (ICZN, 1991).
- [IFS] *Colias hyale* race *calida* s-race *ubercalida* Verity, 1947. Farfalle diurne Italia 3: 266, pl. 35, fig. 8-10.
TL: Saint Zacharie, Vence (SE France).
- [SN] *Colias australis* ssp. *ubercalida* Reissinger, 1959. Nachr.-bl. Bayer. Entomol. 8(12): [118-119](#).
Statut nov. for *Colias hyale calida ubercalida* Verity, 1947.
- [JS] *Colias alfacariensis* ssp. *senonica* Reissinger, 1972. Atalanta 3(9): [359-365](#), [pl. 3](#), [fig. 5-8](#).
TL: Lardy (Seine-et-Oise dep., France).
- [JS] *Colias alfacariensis* ssp. *paracalida* Reissinger, 1972. Atalanta 3(9): [366-369](#), [pl. 4](#), [fig. 3-5](#).
TL: Wels, Wien (Austria).
- [JS] *Colias alfacariensis* ssp. *orthocalida* Reissinger, 1974. Atalanta 5(1): [1-17](#), [pl. 7](#), [fig. 1-4](#).
TL: Allgäuer Alpen, Oberstdorf, Oytal (Bavaria, S Germany).
- [JS] *Colias alfacariensis* ssp. *kantaraica* Reissinger, 1989. Neue Entomol. Nachr. 26: [119-124](#), [pl. 23](#), [fig. 1-7](#).
TL: El-Kantara (Algeria).
- [JS] *Colias alfacariensis* ssp. *bergeri* Reissinger, 1989. Neue Entomol. Nachr. 26: [125-128](#), [pl. 25](#), [fig. 5-8](#).
TL: Ankara (Turkey).
- [JS] *Colias alfacariensis* ssp. *rumilica* Reissinger, 1989. Neue Entomol. Nachr. 26: [129-130](#), [pl. 31](#), [fig. 1-16](#).
TL: Stanimaka (Bulgaria).
- [JS] *Colias alfacariensis* ssp. *fontainei* Reissinger, 1989. Neue Entomol. Nachr. 26: [141-147](#), [pl. 41](#), [fig. 5-8](#).
TL: Borjom (Transcaucasia, Georgia).
- [JS] *Colias alfacariensis* ssp. *remota* Reissinger, 1989. Neue Entomol. Nachr. 26: [148-153](#), [pl. 49](#), [fig. 1-8](#).
TL: Wolsk (Saratov Obl., Russian Federation).
- [JS] *Colias alfacariensis* ssp. *slavonica* Reissinger, 1989. Neue Entomol. Nachr. 26: [153-158](#), [pl. 56](#), [fig. 1-4](#).
TL: Mirovo, Boljevac (E Serbia).
- [JS] *Colias alfacariensis* ssp. *magyarica* Reissinger, 1989. Neue Entomol. Nachr. 26: [159-164](#), [pl. 56](#), [fig. 5-8](#).
TL: Cséhtelek (Bihar Com., W Romania).
- [JS] *Colias alfacariensis* ssp. *vihorlatensis* Reissinger, 1989. Neue Entomol. Nachr. 26: [165-169](#), [pl. 63](#), [fig. 1-4](#).
TL: Remetskä Hämre, Vihorlat (E Slovakia).

[JS] *Colias alfacariensis* ssp. *metacalida* Reissinger, 1989. Neue Entomol. Nachr. 26: [170-173, pl. 63, fig. 5-8](#).
TL: Rovinjsko Selo (Istria, Croatia).

Colias myrmidone (Esper, [1781])

[ORIG] *Papilio myrmidone* Esper, [1781]. Schmett. Abb. Nat. 1(2): [88-89, pl. 65 \(cont. 15\), fig. 1-2](#).

TL: Tyrnau, Hungary (= Trnava, Slovakia).

[JS] *Colias myrmidone* var. *cytisi* Prittowitz, 1842. Ber. Schles. Tauschver. Scmett. 3: 19-21.

TL: Kreisewitz (= Krzyzowice, SW Poland).

[JS] *Colias myrmidone* var. *ermak* Grum-Grshimailo, 1890. Mém. Lépid. 4: [251-252, note](#).

TL: Mias (Tscheljabinskaya distr., Russian Federation).

[JS] *Colias myrmidone* var. *nana* Mayer, 1910. Int. Entomol. Z. 4(33): [182](#).

TL: Graz (Styria, Austria).

[JS] *Colias myrmidone ratisbonensis* Fritsch, 1919. Int. Entomol. Z. 13(1): [7](#).

TL: Regensburg (Bavaria, Germany).

[JS] *Colias myrmidone antschari* Korb, 2005. Cat. Butt. Ex-USSR: 23.

TL: Sormovo (Nizhny Novgorod obl., Russian Federation).

Colias caucasica Staudinger, 1871

[ORIG] *Colias myrmidone* var. *caucasica* Staudinger, 1871. Catal. Lepid. eur. Faunengeb. 1: [6](#).

TL: Georgia.

[JS] *Colias olga* Romanoff, 1882. Horae Soc. Entomol. Ross. 17(1/2): [127-134, pl. 4, fig. 1-4](#).

TL: Borjom d'Achalzich (= Borshom, Georgia) ; Achty (Dagestan Rep., Russian Federation).

[JS] *Colias myrmidone* f. *balcanica* Rebel, 1901. Verh. Zool.-Bot. Ges. Wien 51(2): [134](#).

TL: Vucija Bara (Bosnia and Herzegovina).

Colias aurorina Herrich-Schäffer, [1850]

[ORIG] *Colias aurorina* Herrich-Schäffer, [1850]. Syst. Bearb. Schmett. Eur. 1: [pl. 95, fig. 453-453](#) ; 6 (Nachtrag): [22](#) [1851].

TL: Azerbaijan.

[JS] *Colias tamara* Nordmann, 1851. Bull. Soc. Impér. Nat. Moscou 24(2): [413-416, pl. 11, fig. 2-3](#).

TL: Caucasus (W Azerbaijan).

[JS] *Colias auricoma* Eversmann, 1851. Bull. Soc. Impér. Nat. Moscou 24(2): [622-624](#).

TL: Caucasus (W Azerbaijan).

[JS] *Colias chrysocome* Freyer, [1851]. Neuere Beitr. Schmett. 6(95): [132-133, pl. 566, fig. 1-2](#).

TL: Caucasus.

[JS] *Colias heldreichi* Staudinger, 1862. Entomol. Ztg. 23(4/6): [257-264](#).

TL: Tymfristos Mt. (N Greece).

[JS] *Colias aurora* var. *anna* Gerhard, 1882. Berl. Entomol. Z. 26(1): [125](#).

TL: Achty, Samur River (Daghestan rep., North Caucasus fed. Distr., Russian Federation).

[JS] *Colias aurorina* ssp. *daghestanica* Verhulst J., 1994. Lambillionea 94(1): 115-117, fig. 1-2.

TL: Rutul, Samur River (Daghestan rep., North Caucasus fed. Distr., Russian Federation).

Subfamily

Pierinae Duponchel, [1835]

- [RJ] Pierides Duponchel, [1835]. In Godart, Hist. nat. Lépid. Fr.Suppl. 1(25): [381-382](#).
TG: *Pieris* Schrank, 1801.
- [RJ] Pieridina Herrich-Schäffer, 1853. Samml. Neu. Aussereur. Schmett.: [54](#).
TG: *Pieris* Schrank, 1801.
- [RJ] Pierididae Reuter, [1896]. Acta Soc. Sc. Fenn. 22(1): [228](#).
TG: *Pieris* Schrank, 1801.
- [ICZN] Pieridae Duponchel, [1835]. Opinion 500 (ICZN, 1958. Opin. Declar. Int. Comm. Zool. Nomencl. 17(22): [395-422](#)).
TG: *Pieris* Schrank, 1801.

Tribe

Aporiini Chapman, 1895

- [ORIG] Aporinae Chapman, 1895. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 6(6): [127](#).
TG: *Aporia* Hübner, [1819].

Genus

Belenois Hübner, [1819]

- [ORIG] *Belenois* Hübner, [1819]. Verz. bekannt. Schmett.: [92](#).
TS: *Papilio calypso* Drury, 1773 [African fauna] by monotypy.
- [JS] *Glycestha* Billberg, 1820. Enum. Ins. Mus. Billb.: [76](#).
TS: *Papilio coronea* Cramer, 1775 by subsequent designation by Scudder, 1875. Proc. Amer. Arts Sci. 10(2): 178.
- [JS] *Pseudohuphina* Stoneham, 1940. Bull. Stoneham Mus. (40): 4.
TS: *Pieris raffrayi* Oberthür 1878. Étud. Entomol. ? : 17, pl. 1, fig. 3 by original designation.

Subgenus

Anaphaeis Hübner, [1819]

- [ORIG] *Anaphaeis* Hübner, [1819]. Verz. bekannt. Schmett.: [93](#).
TS: *Papilio creona* Cramer, 1776 [Afrotropical fauna].
- [JS] *Pseudanaphaeis* Bernardi, 1953. Rev. fr. Entomol. 20(1): 50.
TS: *Pieris gidica* Godart, 1819 by original designation.

Belenois aurota (Fabricius, 1793)

- [ORIG] *Papilio aurota* Fabricius, 1793. Entomol. Syst. 3(1): [197](#).
TL: SE India.
- [JH] *Papilio mesentina* Cramer [1780]. Uitl. Kap.3: [140](#), [175](#), [pl. 270](#), [fig. A-B](#).
TL: SE India ; *nec* *Papilio mesentina* Cramer, [1777]. Uitl. Kap. 2: [102](#), [149](#), [pl. 162](#), [fig. B-C](#).
- [JS] *Papilio augusta* Olivier, [1804]. Voyage Emp. Othom. 4: [28-29](#), Atlas 2: [pl. 33](#), [fig. 3 A-B](#).
TL: Beirut (Lebanon).

Genus

Aporia Hübner, [1819]

- [ORIG] *Aporia* Hübner, [1819]. Verz. bekannt. Schmett.: [90](#).
TS: *Papilio crataegi* Linnaeus, 1758 by monotypy.
- [JS] *Pieris* Stephens, 1827. Illust. Br. Entomol.1: [25](#).
TS: *Papilio crataegi* Linnaeus, 1758 by monotypy.
- [JS] *Leuconea* Donzel, 1837. Ann. Soc. Entomol. Fr. 6: [80](#).
TS: *Papilio crataegi* Linnaeus, 1758 by monotypy.
- [JS] *Metaporia* Butler, 1870. Cistula Entomol. 1(3): [38](#), [51](#).
TS: *Pieris agathon* Gray, 1831 by original designation.
- [JS] *Betaporia* Matsumura, 1919. Entomol. Mag. Kyoto 3: [146-147](#), pl. 4.
TS: *Pieris moltrechti* Oberthür, 1909 by original designation.
- [JS] *Futuronerva* Bryk, 1928. Entomol. Z. 42(5): [50](#).
TS: *Futuronerva absurda* Bryk, 1928 (=ab. of *Papilio crataegi* Linnaeus, 1758 ?) by original designation.

Aporia crataegi (Linnaeus, 1758)

- [ORIG] *Papilio crataegi* Linnaeus, 1758. Syst. Nat. (ed. 10)1: [467](#).
TL: Sweden.
- [ND] *Papilio nigro nervosus* Retzius, 1783. Gen. Spec. Ins.: [30](#).
TL: - ; Nomen nudum.
- [JS] *Leuconea crataegi* var. *alepica* Cosmovici, 1892. Naturaliste 14(136): [254](#).
TL: Iași (Romania).
- [JS] *Aporia crataegi* var. *augusta* Turati, 1905. Nat. Sicil. 18(2-3): [26-27](#), pl. 1, fig. 2-4, 6-7.
TL: Ficuzza (Palermo prov., Sicily, S Italy).
- [JS] *Aporia crataegi* ssp. *hyalina* Röber, 1907. In: Seitz, Grossschmett. Erde (1)1: [40](#).
TL: Taurus (Turkey).
- [JS] *Pieris (Aporia) crataegi minor* Verity, [1907]. Rhopal. Palaeart.: 119, pl. 26, fig. 8-9.
TL: Vernet-les-Bains (Pyrénées-Orientales dep., S France).
- [JS] *Aporia crataegi colona* Krulikowsky, 1909. Rev. Russ. Entomol. 9: [293](#).
TL: Viatka (Volga-Vyatka reg., Russian Federation).
- [JS] *Aporia crataegi* race *mauritanica* Oberthür, 1909. Ét. Lépid. comp. 3: [120](#).
TL: Algeria.
- [JS] *Aporia crataegi* ssp. *basanius* Fruhstorfer, 1910. Soc. entomol. 25(13): [50](#).
TL: Alpes Maritimes, Rom, Simplon, Col des Annes, Geneva (France ; Italy ; Switzerland).
- [JH] *Pieris (Aporia) crataegi meridionalis* Verity, [1911]. Rhopal. Palaeart.: 324, pl. 66.
TL: Syria.
- [JS] *Aporia crataegi* ssp. *augustior* Graves, 1925. Trans. entomol. Soc. Lond. 73(1/2): [73-75](#), pl. 5, fig. 10.
TL: Salt, Bir Ayub Road, Jubaiha (Jordanian).
- [JS] *Aporia crataegi* ssp. *karavaievi* Krulikowsky, 1926. Trav. Mus. Zool. Kiev 1: 66, 84.

- TL: Mursinzy (Ukraine).
 [JS] *Futuronerva absurda* Bryk, 1928. Entomol. Z.42(5): [50](#).
 TL: *Futuronerva absurda* Bryk, 1928. Entomol. Z.42(5): [50](#).
 [JS] *Aporia crataegi* f. *fert* Turati & Fiori, 1930. Mem. Soc. entomol. Ital. 9: [197-198](#).
 TL: Castello (Rhodos, Greece).
 [JS] *Aporia crataegi* race *crataegi-augusta* Verity, 1937. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 49(suppl.): [13](#).
 TL: Mt. Olympus (Greece).
 [JS] *Aporia crataegi iranica* Forster, 1939. In: Muksgaard, Lepid. Iran. (1): 1.
 TL: Mt. Talysh (Azerbaijan ; Iran).
 [JS] *Aporia crataegi* ssp. *rutae* Bryk, 1940. Ark. Zool.32A: 3.
 TL: Spain.
 [NN] *Aporia crataegi herodias* Hemming, 1941. Proc. R. entomol. Soc. Lond. 10(10): [208](#).
 Nom. nov. pro *Pieris (Aporia) crataegi meridionalis* Verity, 1911; *nec Pieris napi meridionalis* Heyne, [1895].
 [JH] *Aporia crataegi* ssp. *transiens* Lempke, 1953. Tijdschr. Entomol.96(4): [283](#), [pl. 9, fig. 3-4, 7-8](#).
 TL: Wiessel (Guelderland prov., Netherlands).
 [NN] *Aporia crataegi transitoria* Lempke, 1974. Entomol. Ber. 34(1): [47](#).
 Nom. nov. pro *Aporia crataegi transiens* Lempke, 1953 ; *nec Aporia hippia transiens* Alphéraky, 1897.
 [JS] *Aporia crataegi* ssp. *rotunda* Eitschberger & Reissinger, 1971. Entomol. Z. 81: 32.
 TL: Scanno (S Italy).

Tribe

Pierini Duponchel, [1835]

- [RJ] Pierides Duponchel, [1835]. In Godart, Hist. nat. Lépid. Fr.Suppl. 1(25): [381-382](#).
 TG: *Pieris* Schrank, 1801.
 [RJ] Pieridina Herrich-Schäffer, 1853. Samml. Neu. Aussereur. Schmett.: [54](#).
 TG: *Pieris* Schrank, 1801.
 [RJ] Pierididae Reuter, [1896]. Acta Soc. Sc. Fenn. 22(1): [228](#).
 TG: *Pieris* Schrank, 1801.
 [ICZN] Pieridae Duponchel, [1835]. Opinion 500 (ICZN, 1958. Opin. Declar. Int. Comm. Zool. Nomencl. 17(22): [395-422](#)).
 TG: *Pieris* Schrank, 1801.

Genus

Pontia Fabricius, 1807

- [ORIG] *Pontia* Fabricius, 1807. In: Illiger, Mag. Insektenk. 6: [283](#).
 TS: *Papilio daplidice* Linnaeus, 1758 by Curtis, [1824]. Brit. Entomol. 5: [no. 48](#).
 [IN] *Mancipium* Hübner, [1807]. Samml. exot. Schmett.1: [pl. \[141\]](#).
 TS: *Papilio hellica* Hübner, 1807 (= *Papilio helice* Linnaeus, 1764) by monotypy ; invalid - Opinion 137 (ICZN, 1939: [21-28](#)).
 [JS] *Synchloe* Hübner, 1818. Zutr. Samml. exot. Schmett. 1 : [26](#).
 TS: *Papilio callidice* Hübner, 1800 by subsequent designation by Butler, 1870. Cistula Entomol. 1(3): [51](#).
 [JS] *Mancipium* Stephens, 1827. Illust. Brit. Entomol.1: [22](#).

- TS: *Papilio daplidice* Linnaeus, 1758 by subsequent designation by Koçak, [1982]. Priamus 1(4): [155-156](#).
- [JS] *Parapieris* Nicéville, 1897. J. asiat. Soc. Bengal 66(2)(3): [563](#).
- TS: *Papilio callidice* Hübner, 1800 by original designation.
- [JS] *Leucochloe* Röber, 1907. In: Seitz, Gross-Schmett. Erde (1)1: [49](#).
- TS: *Papilio daplidice* Linnaeus, 1758 by subsequent designation by Klots, [1933]. Entomol. Amer. 12(3): [154](#).
- [JS] *Pontieuchloia* Verity, 1929. Ann. Soc. entomol. Fr. 98(3): [347](#).
- TS: *Papilio chloridice* Hübner, 1813 by monotypy.

Pontia chloridice (Hübner, [1813])

- [ORIG] *Papilio chloridice* Hübner, [1813]. Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 141, fig. 712-715](#).
- TL: Volga (Russian Federation).
- [JH] *Papilio daplidice russiae* Esper, [1784]. Schmett. Abb. Nat. 1(2): [[177](#)], [pl. 90, fig. 1](#).
- TL: Volga (Russian Federation) ; *nec Papilio arge russiae* Esper, [1783].
- [JH] *Pieris chloridice* var. *albidice* Staudinger, 1901. In: Staudinger & Rebel, Cat. Lepid. pal. Faunengeb.: [12](#).
- TL: Schahrud (N Iran) ; *nec Pieris daplidice albidice* Oberthür, 1881.
- [NN] *Pontia chloridice schahrudensis* Koçak, 1980. Nota Lepid. 2 : [139-140](#).
Nom. nov. for *Pieris chloridice* var. *albidice* Staudinger, 1901, *nec* Oberthür, 1881.

Pontia callidice (Hübner, [1800])

- [ORIG] *Papilio callidice* Hübner, [1800]. Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 81, fig. 408-409](#), [1806]: [63](#).
- TL: Switzerland.
- [JS] *Anthocharis callidice* var. *chrysidice* Herrich-Schäffer, [1844]. Syst. Bearb. Schmett. Eur. 1: [97](#), [pl. 44, fig. 200-203](#).
- TL: S Russia (Russian Federation).
- [JS] *Synchloe callidice* ssp. *libanotica* Bernardi, 1965. Bull. Soc. Entomol. Fr. 70 (7-8): [231-232](#).
- TL: Mt. Cedar (Lebanon).
- [JS] *Pontia callidice* ssp. *verdioscurasa* Gómez Bustillo, 1980. SHILAP 8(31): [173-174](#).
- TL: Vallferrera (Lérida prov., N Spain).

Pontia edusa (Fabricius, 1777)

- [ORIG] *Papilio edusa* Fabricius, 1777. Gen. Ins.: [255-256](#).
- TL: *Papilio edusa* Fabricius, 1777. Gen. Ins.: [255-256](#).
- [JS] *Papilio edusa* Fabricius, 1777. Gen. Ins.: [255-256](#).
- TL: Leipzig (Germany).
- [JS] *Leucochloë daplidice* var. *jachontovi* Krulikowsky, 1908. Soc. Entomol. 23(1): [3](#).
- TL: Kazan (Russian Frderation).
- [JS] *Pontia daplidice* race *expansa* Verity, 1919. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 31(5): [87](#).
- TL: Tuscany (Italy).
- [JS] *Pontia daplidice* race *ampla* Verity, 1919. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 31(5): [87](#).
- TL: S. Martino (Sicily, S Italy).

Pontia daplidice (Linnaeus, 1758)

- [ORIG] *Papilio daplidice* Linnaeus, 1758. Syst. Nat. (ed. 10)1: [468](#).
TL: NW Africa.
- [JS] *Papilio belemida* Geyer, [1832]. Samml. eur. Schmett.1: [pl. 189, fig. 931-934](#).
TL: -.
- [JS] *Pieris daplidice* var. *albidice* Oberthür, 1881. Étud. Entomol.6: [47](#).
TL: Algeria, ... Andalusia (S Spain).
- [JS] *Leucochloe daplidice* ssp. *laenas* Fruhstorfer, 1908. Entomol. Z. 22(12): [51](#).
TL: Palestine.
- [JS] *Pontia daplidice iberidice* Bryk, 1940. Ark. Zool. 32A(22): 7.
TL: Sierra Nevada (S Spain).

Pontia glauconome Klug, 1829

- [ORIG] *Pontia glauconome* Klug, 1829. Symb. Phys. (Evertebrata): [\[28\]](#), [pl. 7, fig. 18-19](#).
TL: Mount Sinai (Egypt).

Genus

Pieris Schrank, 1801

- [ORIG] *Pieris* Schrank, 1801. Fauna Boica 2(1): [152](#), [160-170](#).
TS: *Papilio brassicae* Linnaeus, 1758 by subsequent designation by Latreille, 1810. Consid. gén. Ordre nat. Anim.: [351](#), [440](#).
- [IN] *Mancipium* Hübner, 1806. Tentamen: [\[1\]](#).
TS: *Papilio brassicae* Linnaeus, 1758 by monotypy ; not available (Opinion 278 (ICZN, 1954: [135-178](#))).
- [IN] *Danaus* Oken, 1815. Lehrb. Naturgesch. (Zool.) 3(1): [723](#).
TS: *Papilio brassicae* Linnaeus, 1758 by subsequent designation by Crotch, 1872: [60](#) ; not available (Opinion 417 (ICZN, 1956: [1-42](#))).
- [JS] *Ganoris* Dalman, 1816. K. svenska VetenskAkad. Handl.(1b) 1816(1): [61-62](#).
TS: *Papilio brassicae* Linnaeus, 1758 by original designation.
- [JS] *Andropodum* Hübner, 1822. Syst.-alphab. Verz.: [2](#).
TS: *Papilio brassicae* Linnaeus, 1758 by subsequent designation by Hemming, 1933. Entomologist 66(844): 199.
- [JS] *Tachyptera* Berge, 1842. Schmetterlingsbuch: [19, 92-105](#).
TS: *Papilio brassicae* Linnaeus, 1758 by subsequent designation by Hemming, 1934. Entomologist 67(849): 38.

Subgenus

Pieris Schrank, 1801

- [ORIG] *Pieris* Schrank, 1801. Fauna Boica 2(1): [152](#), [160-170](#).
TS: *Papilio brassicae* Linnaeus, 1758 by subsequent designation by Latreille, 1810. Consid. gén. Ordre nat. Anim.: [351](#), [440](#).
- [IN] *Mancipium* Hübner, 1806. Tentamen: [\[1\]](#).
TS: *Papilio brassicae* Linnaeus, 1758 by monotypy ; not available (Opinion 278 (ICZN, 1954: [135-178](#))).
- [IN] *Danaus* Oken, 1815. Lehrb. Naturgesch. (Zool.) 3(1): [723](#).
TS: *Papilio brassicae* Linnaeus, 1758 by subsequent designation by Crotch, 1872: [60](#) ; not available (Opinion 417 (ICZN, 1956: [1-42](#))).
- [JS] *Ganoris* Dalman, 1816. K. svenska VetenskAkad. Handl.(1b) 1816(1): [61-62](#).

TS: *Papilio brassicae* Linnaeus, 1758 by original designation.

[JS] *Andropodum* Hübner, 1822. Syst.-alphab. Verz.: [2](#).

TS: *Papilio brassicae* Linnaeus, 1758 by subsequent designation by Hemming, 1933. Entomologist 66(844): 199.

[JS] *Tachyptera* Berge, 1842. Schmetterlingsbuch: [19, 92-105](#).

TS: *Papilio brassicae* Linnaeus, 1758 by subsequent designation by Hemming, 1934. Entomologist 67(849): 38.

***Pieris brassicae* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

[ORIG] *Papilio brassicae* Linnaeus, 1758. Syst. Nat. (ed. 10)1: [467-468](#).

TL: Sweden.

[JS] *Pontia chariclea* Stephens, 1827. Illust. Brit. Entomol.1: [17-18](#), [pl. \[3\]](#), [fig. 1-2](#).

TL: Hertford (England, UK).

[JS] *Pieris brassicae verna* Zeller, 1847. Isis von Oken 1847(3): [222 \(=220\)](#).

TL: Messina, Sicily (S Italy).

[JS] *Pieris brassicae aestiva* Zeller, 1847. Isis von Oken 1847(3): [222 \(=220\)](#).

TL: Syracuse, Sicily (S Italy).

[JS] *Pieris brassicae* var. *catoleuca* Röber, 1896. Entomol. Nachr. 22(6): [81](#).

TL: Taurus (Turkey).

[JS] *Pieris brassicae* ssp. *cyprica* Verity, 1908. Rhopal. Pal.: 163, pl. 35, fig. 14-15.

TL: Larnaca (Cyprus).

[JS] *Pieris brassicae vazquezi* Oberthür, 1914. Ét. Lépid. Comp. 9(2): [89](#), [pl. 264](#), [fig. 2207](#).

TL: Castille (C Spain).

[JS] *Pieris brassicae* ssp. *azorensis* Rebel, 1917. Ann. Naturh. Mus. Wien 31: [16](#).

TL: Azores (Portugal).

[JS] *Pieris brassicae* f. *italorum* Stauder, 1921. Dt. Entomol. Z. Iris 35(1/2): [26](#).

TL: M. Martinello, Aspromonte (Calabria, S Italy).

[JS] *Mancipium brassicae* f. *cyniphia* Turati, 1924. Atti Soc. ital. Sci. nat. 63: [27-28](#), pl. 1, fig. 2.

TL: Benghazi (Cyrenaica, Libya).

[JS] *Mancipium brassicae subtaeniata* Turati, 1929. Arch. Zool. Ital. 13: 178.

TL: Egeo (=Rhodes), Greece.

[JS] *Mancipium brassicae* f. *alpina* Rocci, 1929. Mem. Soc. Entomol. Ital. 8(1): [97](#).

TL: Piedmont (NW Italy).

***Pieris wollastoni* (Butler, 1886)**

[ORIG] *Ganoris wollastoni* Butler, 1886. Ann. Mag. Nat. hist. Zool. Bot. Geol. (5)17: [430](#).

TL: Madeira (Portugal).

***Pieris cheiranthi* (Hübner, [1808])**,

[ORIG] *Papilio cheiranthi* Hübner, [1808]. Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 127](#), [fig. 647-648](#), [1824]: [4](#).

TL: Tenerife (Canary Islands, Spain).

[JS] *Pieris cheiranthi benchoavensis* Pinker, 1968. Z. Arb. Öst. Entomol. 20: [22-24](#), [fig.](#)

TL: Los Sauces, La Palma (Canary Islands, Spain).

Subgenus

Artogeia Verity, 1947

[ORIG] *Pieris (Artogeia)* Verity, 1947. Farfalle diurne Italia 3: [192-193](#).

TS: *Papilio napi* Linnaeus, 1758 by original designation.

Pieris krueperi Staudinger, 1860

[ORIG] *Pieris krueperi* Staudinger, 1860. Wiener entomol. Monatschr. 4(1): [19-20](#).

TL: Greece.

[JS] *Pieris krueperi syra* Verity, [1911]. Rhopal. Pal. : 336, pl. 67, fig. 20-21.

TL: Shar Deresy (Syria).

Pieris rapae (Linnaeus, 1758)

[ORIG] *Papilio rapae* Linnaeus, 1758. Syst. Nat. (ed. 10)1: [468](#).

TL: Sweden.

[JS] *Papilio nelo* Bergsträsser, 1779. Nom. Ins.2: [47-48](#), [pl. 32, fig. 2](#).

TL: Germany.

[JS] *Pontia metra* Stephens, 1827. Illust. Brit. Entomol.1: [19-20](#).

TL: Hertford, Ripley (England, UK).

[JS] *Pieris rapae syracusana* Zeller, 1847. Isis von Oken 1847(3): [221](#).

TL: Syracuse (Sicily, S Italy).

[JS] *Pieris rapae messanensis* Zeller, 1847. Isis von Oken 1847(3): [221](#).

TL: Messina (Sicily, S Italy).

[JS] *Pieris rapae* var. *leucotera* Stefanelli, 1869. Boll. Soc. Entomol. Ital 1: [147](#).

TL: Florence (Tuscany, Italy).

[JS] *Pieris rapae leucosoma* Schawerda 1905. Verh. Zool.-Bot. Ges. Wien 55: [516](#).

TL: Beirut (Lebanon).

[JS] *Pieris rapae mauretanicus* Verity, [1908]. Rhopal. Pal.: 155, pl. 33, fig. 43-44.

TL: Algeria ; Tangier (N Morocco).

[JS] *Pieris rapae* f. (ssp.?) *atomaria* Fruhstorfer, 1909. Entomol. Z. 23(8): [42](#).

TL: Dalmatia (Croatia).

[JS] *Pieris rapae transcaucasica* Stauder, 1925. Entomol. Anz. 5(1): [3-4](#).

TL: Jelisavetpol (Azerbaijan).

[JS] *Pieris rapae originalis* Bryk, 1940. Ark. Zool. 32A(22): 4, pl. 2, fig. 4.

TL: Spain.

Pieris mannii (Mayer, 1851)

[ORIG] *Pontia mannii* Mayer, 1851. Entomol. Ztg. 12(5): [151](#).

TL: Split (Croatia).

[IFS] *Pieris rapae* ab. *todaroana* Pincitore Marott, 1879. Giorn. Sci. Nat., Palermo 14: [51-52](#).

- TL: Sicily (S Italy).
[JS] *Pieris rapae* race *rossii* Stefanelli, 1900. Bull. Soc. Entomol. Ital. 32: [178-179](#).
- TL: Tuscany (Italy).
[JS] *Pieris manni* race *rossiandegava* Delahaye, 1910. Pieris Manni Maine-et-Loire: [1-15](#).
- TL: Angoulême (W France).
[JS] *Pieris manni* race *alpigena* Verity, [1919]. Rhopal. Pal.: 336.
- TL: Aosta (NW Italy).
[JS] *Pieris manni* race *creta* Verity, 1919. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 31(5): [88](#).
- TL: Mount Fanna, Florence, Isle of Elba (Italy).
[JS] *Pieris manni* ssp. *neglecta* Stauder, 1921. Mitt. Münch. Entomol. Ges. 12(1-6): [21-22](#).
- TL: Bolzano (Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol, NE Italy).
[JS] *Pieris manni* f. *pedemontana* Rocci, 1929. Mem. Soc. Entomol. Ital. 8(1): [105](#).
- TL: Subalpine Italy.
[JS] *Pieris manni* race *veragra* Verity, 1935. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 47(suppl.): [44](#).
- TL: Lavey-les-Bains, Martigny (Switzerland).
[JS] *Pieris (Artogeia) manni* race *todaroana* Verity, 1948. Farfalle diurne Italia 3: 225-226.
Stat. nov. for *Pieris rapae* ab. *todaroana* Pincitore Marott, 1879.
- [JS] *Pieris (Artogeia) manni* race *hemiandegava* Verity, 1948. Farfalle diurne Italia 3: 228.
TL: Vernet-les-Bains (Pyrénées-Orientales dep., S France).
- [JS] *Pieris (Artogeia) manni* race *cisalpina* Verity, 1948. Farfalle diurne Italia 3: 229-230, pl. , fig. 27-29.
TL: Torino, Nuove Terme di Acqui (Italy).
- [JS] *Pieris manni* ssp. *haroldi* Wyatt, 1952. Z. wien. Entomol. Ges.37: [173](#), pl. [21B](#), fig. [5-6](#).
TL: Taghzeft-Paß (Middle Atlas, Morocco).
- [JS] *Pieris manni* ssp. *reskovitsi* Gozmány, 1968. Faun. Hung. 91: [41-42](#).
TL: Hungary.
- [SR] *Pieris manni* ssp. *roberti* Eitschberger & Steiniger, 1973. Entomol. Z.83(6): 65, pl.
TL: La Peza (Granada prov., S Spain).
- [JS] *Pieris manni* race *creta* Verity, 1919. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 31(5): [88](#).
TL: Mount Fanna, Florence, Isle of Elba (Italy).
- [JS] *Pieris manni* ssp. *neglecta* Stauder, 1921. Mitt. Münch. Entomol. Ges. 12(1-6): [21-22](#).
TL: Bolzano (Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol, NE Italy).
- [JS] *Pieris manni* f. *pedemontana* Rocci, 1929. Mem. Soc. Entomol. Ital. 8(1): [105](#).
TL: Subalpine Italy.
- [JS] *Pieris manni* race *veragra* Verity, 1935. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 47(suppl.): [44](#).
TL: Lavey-les-Bains, Martigny (Switzerland).
- [JS] *Pieris (Artogeia) manni* race *todaroana* Verity, 1948. Farfalle diurne Italia 3: 225-226.
Stat. nov. for *Pieris rapae* ab. *todaroana* Pincitore Marott, 1879.
- [JS] *Pieris (Artogeia) manni* race *hemiandegava* Verity, 1948. Farfalle diurne Italia 3: 228.
TL: Vernet-les-Bains (Pyrénées-Orientales dep., S France).
- [JS] *Pieris (Artogeia) manni* race *cisalpina* Verity, 1948. Farfalle diurne Italia 3: 229-230, pl. , fig. 27-29.

- TL: Torino, Nuove Terme di Acqui (Italy).
 [JS] *Pieris manni* ssp. *haroldi* Wyatt, 1952. Z. wien. Entomol. Ges.37: [173, pl. 21B, fig. 5-6](#).
 TL: Taghzeft-Paß (Middle Atlas, Morocco).
 [JS] *Pieris manni* ssp. *reskovitsi* Gozmány, 1968. Faun. Hung. 91: [41-42](#).
 TL: Hungary.
 [SR] *Pieris manni* ssp. *roberti* Eitschberger & Steiniger, 1973. Entomol. Z.83(6): 65, pl.
 TL: La Peza (Granada prov., S Spain).

***Pieris ergane* (Geyer, [1828])**

- [ORIG] *Papilio ergane* Geyer, [1828]. In: Hübner, Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 184, fig. 904-907](#).
 TL: Ragusa (Sicily, Italy).
 [JS] *Pontia narcaea* Freyer, 1828. Beitr. Gesch. eur. Schmett.1(8): [147, pl. 43, fig. 2](#).
 TL: Dalmatia (Croatia), Florence (Italy).
 [JS] *Pontia rapae* var. *minor* Costa, [1836]. Fauna Reg. Nap. Lepid.: [[32](#)], (Lep. Diurn) [pl. 3, fig. 3-4](#).
 TL: Aspromonte, Gran Sasso (C Italy).
 [JS] *Pieris ergane* f. *rostagnoi* Verity, [1908]. Rhopal. Pal.: 153, pl. 33, fig. 27-31.
 TL: Oricola (Abruzzo, C Italy).
 [JS] *Pieris ergane* f. *stefanellii* Verity, [1908]. Rhopal. Pal.: 153, pl. 33, fig. 32-35.
 TL: Attica (C Greece).
 [JS] *Pieris ergane* f. *detersa* Verity, [1908]. Rhopal. Pal.: 153, pl. 34, fig. 26.
 TL: Barud Dagħ (Turkey).
 [JS] *Pieris ergane italica* Turati, 1910. Atti Soc. Ital. nat. Milano 49: [49](#).
 TL: C Italy.
 [JS] *Pieris ergane* race *exigua* Verity & Querci, 1923. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 35(suppl.): [18](#).
 TL: Fargno Valley, Sibillini Mts. (C Italy).
 [JS] *Pieris ergane* var. *gallia* Mezger, 1932. Lambillionea 32: [156](#).
 TL: Villefranche-de-Confluent (Pyrénées-Orientales dep., S France).
 [JS] *Pieris ergane lucieni* Dujardin, 1951. Bull. Soc. Entomol. Mulhouse 7: 29.
 TL: Briançon (Hautes-Alpes dep., S France).
 [JS] *Artogeia ergane carmelae* Domènech I Torres, 1979. Treb. Soc. Catal. Lepid. 2: [72-74, fig.](#)
 TL: Camarasa (Lleida prov., NE Spain).

***Pieris bryoniae* (Hübner, [1806])**

- [ORIG] *Papilio bryoniae* Hübner, [1806]. Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [62, pl. 81, fig. 407 \(P. naph\)](#).
 TL: Geneva (Switzerland).
 [JS] *Pieris bryoniae* f. *flavescens* Müller, 1933. Int. Entomol. Z. 27(9): [93](#).
 TL: Mödling (Austria).
 [JS] *Pieris bryoniae* ssp. *marani* Moucha, 1956. Bull. Soc. Entomol. Mulhouse 1956: [62-63](#).
 TL: Zádiel (Košice reg., Slovakia).
 [JS] *Pieris bryoniae* ssp. *vihorlatensis* Moucha, 1956. Bull. Soc. Entomol. Mulhouse 1956: [66-67](#).

- TL: Mts. Vihorlat, Remetské Hamre (Košice reg., Slovakia).
 [JS] *Pieris bryoniae* ssp. *carpathensis* Moucha, 1956. Bull. Soc. Entomol. Mulhouse 1956: [64, 66](#).
 TL: Osa (=? Osádka, Žilina reg., Slovakia).
 [JS] *Pieris [bryoniae] caucasica* Lorković, [1969]. Bioloski Glasnik 21: 124-125.
 TL: Caucasus.
 [JS] *Pieris bryoniae* ssp. *turcica* Eitschberger & Hesselbarth, 1977. Atalanta 8(2): [148-150, fig.](#)
 TL: Ilgaz dağı (Çankırı prov., Turkey).
 [JS] *Pieris bryoniae* ssp. *wolfsbergeri* Eitschberger, [1984]. Herbiopoliana 1(1): [154-160](#), (2): [pl. 419, fig. 20-23](#).
 TL: Termi di Valdieri, S. Giovanni (Piedmont, NW Italy).
 [JS] *Pieris bryoniae* ssp. *lorkovici* Eitschberger, [1984]. Herbiopoliana 1(1): [161-168](#), (2): [pl. 423, fig. 17-22](#).
 TL: Vršič (Julian Alps, Slovenia).
 [JS] *Pieris bryoniae* ssp. *goergneri* Eitschberger, 1986. Atalanta 16: [256-257, 261-262, pl. 1, fig. 1-9](#).
 TL: Karadağ-Osthang (Hakkari prov., Turkey).
 [JS] *Pieris bryoniae* ssp. *debrosi* Eitschberger, 1986. Atalanta 16: [262-264, pl. 2, fig. 1-9](#).
 TL: Forêt de la Frasse (Jura, E France).

Pieris napi (Linnaeus, 1758)

- [ORIG] *Papilio napi* Linnaeus, 1758. Syst. Nat. (ed. 10)1: [468](#).
 TL: Sweden.
 [JS] *Papilio napaea* Esper, [1804]. Schmett. Abb. Nat. Suppl. 1(1): [119, pl. 116, fig. 5](#).
 TL: -.
 [JS] *Pontia sabellicae* Stephens, 1827. Illust. Brit. Entomol. 1: [21-22, pl. 3, fig. 3-4](#).
 TL: Battersea Fields (UK).
 [JS] *Pontia glazensis* Schilling, 1831. Uebersicht Arb. Veränd. Schles. Ges. 1830: [93](#).
 TL: Ratibor (Racibórz, Poland).
 [JS] *Pontia napi* var. *intermedia* Krulikowsky, 1844. Bull. Soc. Imp. Nat. Moscou NS 4(2): [211-212, pl. 8, fig. a](#).
 TL: Viatka (Russian Federation).
 [JS] *Pieris napi* var. *meridionalis* Heyne, 1895. Pal. Grossschmett. Naturg. 1(Nachtr.): [714](#).
 TL: C Italy.
 [JS] *Pieris napi* var. *pseudorapae* Verity, 1908. Rhop. Pal.: 144, pl. 32, fig. 23-24.
 TL: Beyrouth (Lebanon).
 [JS] *Pieris napi* ssp. *leovigilda* Fruhstorfer, 1909. Int. Entomol. Z. 3(16): [88](#).
 TL: Savoie (E France), Lausanne (Switzerland).
 [JS] *Pieris napi napi* race *britannica* Verity, 1911. Rhop. Pal.: 332, pl. 32, fig. 4, 6.
 TL: Scotland (UK).
 [JS] *Pieris napi napi* race *maura* Verity, 1911. Rhop. Pal.: 332, pl. 59, fig. 18-20.
 TL: Glacières de Blida (Algeria).
 [JS] *Pieris napi* race *vulgaris* Verity, 1913. J. Linn. Soc. Zool. Lond., Zool. 32: [177](#).
 TL: Florence (Italy).
 [JS] *Pieris napi* ssp. *atlantica* Rothschild, 1917. Novit. Zool. 24: [75](#).

- TL: Glacières de Blida (Algeria).
 [JS] *Pieris napaeae atlantis* Oberthür, 1925. Étud. Lépid. Comp. 22(2): 58-59, pl. 593, fig. 5014-5016.
- TL: Toumliline, Azrou (Morocco).
 [JS] *Pieris napi* race *microvulgaris* Verity, 1927. Bull. Soc. entomol. Fr. 1927: [172-173](#).
- TL: Aldeire, Verez del Marquesado (Sierra Nevada, S Spain).
 [JS] *Pieris napi lusitanica* Sousa, 1926. Duas nov. Subsp. Lepid. Portug.: [1-2](#).
- TL: Porto, Penafiel, Castello de Paiva, Caldellas e Gerez (N Portugal).
 [JS] *Pieris napi suffusa* Sheljuzhko, 1931. Int. Entomol. Z. 25(6): [73](#).
- TL: Caucasus (Azerbaijan).
 [JS] *Pieris napi* ssp. *mirabilis* Bryk, 1940. Arkiv Zool. 32A(22): 5, pl. 2, fig. 6-7.
- TL: Cintra (Portugal).
 [JS] *Pieris napi* race *thomsoni* Warren, 1968. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 80(12): 301-302.
- TL: Scotland (UK).
 [JS] *Pieris napi* ssp. *migueli* Eitschberger, [1984]. Herbiopoliana 1(1): [94-98](#), 1(2): [pl. 399, fig. 5-32](#).
- TL: Peña de la Hoz, Dobres, Fuente Dé (Picos de Europa, Cantabria, N Spain).
 [JS] *Pieris napi* ssp. *santateresae* Eitschberger, [1984]. Herbiopoliana 1(1): [99-102](#), 1(2): [pl. 401, fig. 9-28](#).
- TL: Cuevas del Valle (Sierra de Gredos, Avila prov., C Spain).
 [JS] *Pieris napi* ssp. *carlosi* Eitschberger, [1984]. Herbiopoliana 1(1): [103-104](#), 1(2): [pl. 401, fig. 29-32](#).
- TL: Lapeza, Camino de Carbonales (Granada prov., S Spain).
 [JS] *Pieris napi* ssp. *napoleon* Eitschberger, [1989]. Atalanta 20: [221-228, fig.](#)
- TL: E Ghisoni (Corsica, S France).

ESU *P. adalwinda* Fruhstorfer, 1909

- [ORIG] [*Pieris bryoniae*] *adalwinda* Fruhstorfer, 1909. Int. Entomol. Z. 3(16): [88](#).
 TL: Porsanger (Finnmark county, Norway).
 [JS] *Pieris napi* ssp. *bicolorata* Petersen, 1947. Zool. Bidr. Uppsala 26: 361.
 TL: Murjek (Lapland, Sweden).

Pieris segonzaci Le Cerf, 1923

- [ORIG] *Pieris napi* ssp. *segonzaci* Le Cerf, 1923. Bull. Soc. entomol. Fr. 1923(15): [197](#).
 TL: upper valley of Ourika (High Atlas Mts., Morocco).

Pieris balcana Lorković, [1969]

- [ORIG] *Pieris balcana* Lorković, [1969]. Bioloski Glasnik 21(1-4): 114-120, fig.
 TL: Treska river (N Macedonia).

Tribe

Teracolini Reuter, 1896

- [ORIG] Teracolidi Reuter, 1896. Acta Soc. Sci. Fenn. 22(1): [236](#).
 TG: *Teracolus* Swainson, [1833].
 [JS] Colotini Zerny & Beier, 1936. In: Kükenthal & Krumbach, Handb. Zool. 4(2): 1718.

TG: *Colotis* Hübner, [1819].

Genus

Colotis Hübner, [1819]

- [ORIG] *Colotis* Hübner, [1819]. Verz. bekannt. Schmett.: [97](#).
TS: *Papilio amata* Fabricius, 1775 by subsequent designation by Scudder, 1875. Proc. Amer. Acad. Arts Sci. 10(2): [146](#).
- [JH] *Aphrodite* Hübner, [1819]. Verz. bekannt. Schmett.: [95](#).
TS: *Papilio euippe* Linnaeus, 1758 ; *nec Aphrodite* Link, 1807.
- [JS] *Idmais* Boisduval, 1836. Hist. Nat. Ins. Spec. gén. Lépid. 1: [584-585](#).
TS: *Pontia chrysonome* Klug, 1835 by subsequent designation by Scudder, 1875. Proc. Amer. Acad. Arts Sci. 10(2): [196](#).
- [JH] *Calais* Boisduval, 1836. Hist. Nat. Ins. Spec. gén. Lépid. 1: [584-585](#).
[JS] of *Idmais* Boisduval, 1836 ; [JH] *nec Calais* Rafinesque, 1815.
- [JS] *Callosune* Doubleday, [1847]. In: Doubleday & Westwood, Gen. Diurn. Lepid.: [57](#).
TS: *Papilio danae* Fabricius, 1775 by subsequent designation by Scudder, 1875. Proc. Amer. Acad. Arts Sci. 10(2): [132](#).
- [JS] *Anthopsyche* Wallengren, 1857. Kongl. Svenska Vetensk.-Akad. Handl. 2(4): [10-11](#).
TS: *Papilio achine* Stoll, 1781 by subsequent designation by Scudder, 1875. Proc. Amer. Acad. Arts Sci. 10(2): [114](#).
- [JH] *Ptychopteryx* Wallengren, 1857. Kongl. Svenska Vetensk.-Akad. Handl. 2(4): [17-18](#).
TS: *Ptychopteryx bohemani* Wallengren, 1857 by monotypy ; *nec Ptychopteryx* Leach, 1817.
- [NN] *Thespia* Wallengren, 1858. Öfvers. Kongl. Vetensk.-Akad. Förh. 15(2): [76-77](#).
TS: *Thespia bohemani* Wallengren, 1857 by monotypy ; Nom. nov. for *Ptychopteryx* Wallengren, 1857.
- [JS] *Calicharis* Oberthür, 1876. Étud. Entomol. 1: [18-19](#).
TS: *Anthocharis delphine* Boisduval, 1836 by subsequent designation by Hemming, 1939. Proc. R. Entomol. Soc. Lond. B 8(7): 135.
- [JS] *Madais* Swinhoe, 1909. In: Moore, Lepid. Indica 7(79): [152](#).
TS: *Papilio fausta* Olivier, 1807 by original designation.

Colotis evagore (Klug, 1829)

- [ORIG] *Pontia evagore* Klug, 1829. Symb. Phys. (Evertebrata): [\[28\]](#), [pl. 8, fig. 5-6](#).
TL: Arabia.
- [JS] *Anthocharis nouna* Lucas, 1849. Explor. Scient. Algérie, Hist. nat. Anim. articul. 3: [350-351](#), [pl. 1, fig. 2, 2a-b](#).
TL: Oran (Algeria).
- [JS] *Teracolus दौरا* var. *biskrensis* Blachier, 1908. Ann. Soc. Entomol. Fr. 77(2): [212-214](#).
TL: Biskra (Algeria).
- [JS] *Teracolus lefevrei* Oberthür, 1922. Étud. Lépid. Comp. 19: [30-31](#), [pl. 530, fig. 4401](#).
TL: Azrou (Fez-Meknes reg., Morocco).
- [JS] *Colotis evagore* ssp. *granadensis* Pascual Linares, 1985. SHILAP 12(48): [339-340](#).
TL: Moreleda de Zafayona (Granada prov., S Spain).

Colotis liagore (Klug, 1829)

- [ORIG] *Pontia liagore* Klug, 1829. Symb. Phys. (Evertebrata): [\[24\]](#), [pl. 6, fig. 5-8](#).
TL: Ambukohl (Sudan).

Colotis danae (Fabricius, 1775)

- [ORIG] *Papilio danae* Fabricius, 1775. Syst. entomol.: [476](#).
TL: E India.
- [JS] *Pontia eupompe* Klug, 1829. Symb. Phys. (Evertebrata): [\[25\]](#), [pl. 6, fig. 11-14](#).
TL: Arabia desert (Saudi Arabia), Mt. Sinai (Egypt), Dongola (Sudan), Abyssinia (Ethiopia).

Colotis fausta (Olivier, [1804])

- [ORIG] *Papilio fausta* Olivier, [1804]. Atlas Voyage Emp. Othom. 2: [vii](#), [pl. 33, fig. 4](#).
TL: Lebanon.
- [JS] *Idmais faustina* Felder & Felder, 1865. Reise Novara (Zool.) Lepid. 2: [190](#).
TL: -.

Colotis calais (Cramer, 1775)

- [ORIG] *Papilio calais* Cramer, 1775. Uitl. Kapellen 1: [84](#), [pl. 53, fig. C, D](#).
TL: Northern Cape (South Africa).
- [JS] *Pontia dynamene* Klug, 1829. Symb. Phys. (Evertebrata): [\[25-26\]](#), [pl. 6, fig. 16-18](#).
TL: Arabia desert (Saudi Arabia), Ambukohl (Sudan).

Colotis phisadia (Godart, 1819)

- [ORIG] *Pieris phisadia* Godart, 1819. Encycl. Méth. Entomol. 9(1): [132](#).
TL: uncertain [Senegal or Arabia ?].
- [JS] *Idmais phisadia* var. *palaestinensis* Staudinger, 1897. Dt. Entomol. Z. 10: [271-272](#).
TL: Ain-Dschiddi (Palestine).

Colotis chrysonome (Klug, 1829)

- [ORIG] *Pontia chrysonome* Klug, 1829. Symb. Phys. (Evertebrata): [\[27\]](#), [pl. 7, fig. 9-11](#).
TL: Sudan.
- [JS] *Teracolus chrysonome* ssp. *meinertzhageni* Riley, 1934. Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist. (10)13: 178.
TL: Ahaggar Mountains, Tamanrasset Wadi, Tirarat Plateau (Algeria).
- [JS] *Colotis chrysonome* ssp. *socnensis* Krüger, 1939. Ann. Mus. Libic. Stor. Nat. 1: 321.
TL: Gebel es-Soda, Bir Gteifa (Libya).

Tribe

Anthocharini Scudder, 1889

- [ORIG] Anthocharidi Scudder, 1889. Butt. east U.S. & Canada 2: [1039](#).
TG: *Anthocharis* Boisduval, Rambur & Graslin, [1833].
- [JH] Anthocharidi Tutt, 1896. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 7(12): [301](#).
TG: *Anthocharis* Boisduval, Rambur & Graslin, [1833].

- [JH] Anthocharitini Reuter, 1896. Acta Soc. Sci. Fenn. 22(1): [236-238](#).
TG: *Anthocharis* Boisduval, Rambur & Graslin, [1833].
- [JS] Euchloini Klots, 1930. Bull. Brooklyn Entomol. Soc. 25(2): [80](#).
TG: *Euchloe* Hübner, [1819].

Genus

Euchloe Hübner, [1819]

- [ORIG] *Euchloe* Hübner, [1819]. Verz. bekannt. Schmett.: [94](#).
TS: *Euchloe ausonia* var. *esper*i Kirby, 1871 (= *Euchloe crameri* Butler, 1869) by subsequent designation by ICZN, Opinion [270](#).

Subgenus

Euchloe Hübner, [1819]

- [ORIG] *Euchloe* Hübner, [1819]. Verz. bekannt. Schmett.: [94](#).
TS: *Euchloe ausonia* var. *esper*i Kirby, 1871 (= *Euchloe crameri* Butler, 1869) by subsequent designation by ICZN, Opinion [270](#).

Euchloe insularis (Staudinger, 1861)

- [ORIG] *Antocharis* [sic] *tagis* var. *insularis* Staudinger, 1861. Cat. Lepid. Eur.: [2](#).
TL: Sardinia (Italy) ; Corsica (S France).
- [JS] *Anthocharis tagis* var. *sardoa* Oberthür, 1909. Ét. lépid. comp.3: [145](#).
TL: Sardinia (Italy).

Euchloe crameri Butler, 1869

- [ORIG] *Euchloe crameri* Butler, 1869. Entomol. mon. mag. 5: [271](#).
TL: Spain.
- [JH] *Papilio belia* Stoll, [1782]. In: Cramer, Uitl. Kap. 4: [225-226](#), [248](#), pl. [397](#), fig. A-B.
TL: Provence, Languedoc (S France) ; nec *Papilio belia* Linnaeus, 1767. Syst. Nat.(ed. 12) 1(2): [761](#).
- [JS] *Euchloe ausonia* var. *esper*i Kirby, 1871. Synonym. Cat. Diurn. Lepid.: [506](#).
TL: SW Europa.
- [IFS] *Euchloe belia* ab. *alhambra* Ribbe, 1905. Soc. Entomol. 20: [137](#).
TL: Rio Darro, Granada (Andalusia, S Spain).
- [JS] *Euchloe belia* var. *matutia* Turati, 1907. Nat. Sicil. 18(2-3): [28-29](#), pl. [2](#), fig. [4-12](#).
TL: S. Remo, Bordighera (Liguria, NW Italy).
- [JS] *Euchloe belia* var. *occidentalis* Verity, [1908]. Rhopal. Pal.: 175, nota.
TL: SW Europa, N Africa.
- [SN] *Euchloe belia* var. *alhambrae* Verity, [1908]. Rhopal. Pal.: 176.
TL: Granada (Andalusia, S Spain) ; Stat. nov. for *Euchloe belia* ab. *alhambra* Ribbe, 1905.
- [JS] *Euchloe ausonia genuensis* Rocci, 1920. Atti Soc. Ligust. Sci. Nat. Geogr. 30: 175.
TL: Genova (NW Italy).
- [JS] *Euchloe crameri* ssp. *rifensis* Back, 2008. Entomol. Z. 118: 149.
TL: Chefchaouen (Rif, Morocco).

[JS] *Euchloe ausonia* ssp. *galloiberica* Leraut, 2016. Pap. jour Eur.: [119, pl. 134, fig. 3-13](#).
TL: SW Europa.

***Euchloe melanochloros* Röber, 1907**

[ORIG] *Euchloe belia* f. [race] *melanochloros* Röber, 1907. In: Seitz, Gross-Schmet. Erde (1)1: [52, pl. 3, fig. 3-5](#).
TL: Batna (Algeria).

[JS] *Euchloe tagis* f.[var.] *mauretanicus* Röber, 1907. In: Seitz, Gross-Schmet. Erde (1)1: [53, pl. 22, fig. D\[5\]](#).
TL: Algeria.

[JS] *Anthocharis tagis* var. *algerica* Oberthür, 1909. Ét. lépid. comp.3: [145](#).
TL: Mécheria (Algeria).

[JS] *Euchloe belia* ssp. *paravicinii* Stauder, 1915. Dt. Entomol. Z. Iris 29(1): [25-27](#).
TL: Djebel Aurès, El Kantara (Algeria).

[JS] *Euchloe ausonia* var. *libyca* Turati, 1917. Bull. Soc. entomol. Fr. 1917(9): [161-163, fig. 1](#).
TL: Libya.

[JS] *Euchloe belia* race *aegyptiaca* Verity, [1911]. Rhop. Pal.: 337.
TL: Wadi Hof Heluan (Egypt).

***Euchloe simplonia* (Freyer, 1829)**

[ORIG] *Pontia simplonia* Freyer, 1829. Beitr. Gesch. eur. Schmett. 2(13): [87-89](#), pl. 73, [fig. 2](#).
TL: 'Croatia' (neotype from S Switzerland).

[JS] *Papilio marchandae* Geyer, [1832]. In: Hübner, Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 188, fig. 926-928](#).
TL: -.

[JS] *Anthocharis simplonia* var. *flavidior* Wheeler, 1903. Butt. Switz.: [63](#).
TL: Lavey,... Sierre (Vaud and Valais, Switzerland).

[JS] *Euchloe simplonia* var. *ticina* Vorbrodt & Müller-Rutz, 1911. Schmett. Schweiz 1: [23](#).
TL: Airolo, Faido,... (Ticino, Switzerland).

[IFS] *Euchloe belia* var. *simplonia* f. *oberthueri* Verity, [1911]. Rhopal. Pal.: 179.
TL: Gèdre (Hautes-Pyrénées dep., S France).

[SN] *Euchloe ausonia* *oberthueri* Rothschild, 1914. Novit. Zool. 21(4): [303](#).
Stat. nov. for *Euchloe belia simplonia oberthueri* Verity, [1911]. Rhopal. Pal.: 179.

***Euchloe ausonia* (Hübner, [1804])**

[ORIG] *Papilio ausonia* Hübner, [1804]. Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 113, fig. 582-583](#), [1806]: [64-65](#).
TL: Italy.

[JS] *Anthocharis belia* var. *volgensis* Krulikowsky, 1897. Saratov. zemelsk. Nedel. 1897(1/2): [3-4, pl. 2, fig. 1-2](#).
TL: Saratov (S european Russian Federation).

[JS] *Euchloe belia* var. *uralensis* Bartel, 1903. Dt. entomol. Z. Iris 15: [188-189](#).
TL: S Ural (Russian Federation).

[JS] *Anthocharis belia* var. *romana* Calberla, 1887. Corresp.-Blatt Entomol. Ver. Iris 1887(4): [123](#).
TL: Tivoli (Lazio, C Italy).

- [JS] *Euchloe belia* var. *matutia* Turati, 1905. Nat. Sicil. 18(2-3): [28-29](#), [pl. 2](#), [fig. 7-12](#).
TL: San Remo, Bordighera (Liguria, NW Italy).
- [JS] *Euchloe belia* var. *kruegeri* Turati, 1905. Nat. Sicil. 18(2-3): [29-30](#), [pl. 3](#), [fig. 1-6](#).
TL: Palermo (Sicily, S Italy).
- [JS] *Euchloe belia* var. *trinacriae* Turati, 1905. Nat. Sicil. 18(2-3): [31](#), [pl. 4](#), [fig. 3-6](#).
TL: Madonie (Sicily, S Italy).
- [JS] *Euchloe belia* f. [var.] *taurica* Röber, 1907. In: Seitz, Gross-Schmett. Erde(1)1: [52](#).
TL: Taurus (S Turkey).
- [JS] *Euchloe belia* var. *graeca* Verity, 1908. Rhopal. Pal.: 175.
TL: Mount Parnassus (Greece).
- [JS] *Euchloe belia* ssp. *melisande* Fruhstorfer, 1908. Entomol. Z. 22(12): [51](#).
TL: Palestine.
- [JS] *Euchloe ausonia* f. *interjecta* Stauder, 1925. Soc. Entomol. 40(2): [5](#).
TL: Aspromonte (S Italy).
- [JS] *Euchloe ausonia* ssp. *sovinskyi* Sheljuzhko, 1928. Lepid. Rundsch. 2(7): [75](#).
TL: Lake Elton (Volgograd obl., Russian Federation).
- [JS] *Euchloe belia* var. *gigantea* Caradja, 1931. Mem. Sect. stiint. Acad. Rom. (3)7(8): 308.
TL: Romania.
- [JS] *Euchloe ausonia* ssp. *kastellorisii* Kattulas & Koutsaftikis, 1978. Biol. Gallo-Hellen. 7: 153.
TL: Kastellorizo Isl. (S Aegean, Greece).

***Euchloe eversi* Stamm, 1963**

- [ORIG] *Euchloe belemia* ssp. *everisi* Stamm, 1963. Entomol. Z. 73(6): [47-48](#), [fig. 1-2](#).
TL: Tenerife (Canary Isl., Spain).

***Euchloe grancanariensis* Acosta, 2008**

- [ORIG] *Euchloe belemia* ssp. *grancanariensis* Acosta, 2008. SHILAP 36(142): [176-178](#), [fig. 2](#), [7-12](#).
TL: Gran Canaria (Canary Isl., Spain).
- [JS] *Euchloe constantini* Back, 2008. Entomol. Z. 118(4) : 148.
TL: Gran Canaria (Canary Isl., Spain).

***Euchloe hesperidum* Rothschild, 1913**

- [ORIG] *Euchloe belemia* ssp. *hesperidum* Rothschild, 1913. Novit. Zool. 20: [111](#).
TL: Fuerteventura (Canary Isl., Spain).

***Euchloe belemia* (Esper, [1800])**

- [ORIG] *Papilio belemia* Esper, [1800]. Schmett. Abb. Nat. Suppl. 1(1): [92-93](#), [pl. 110 \(cont. 65\)](#), [fig. 2](#).
TL: Belem (Portugal).
- [JS] *Papilio glauca* Hübner, [1804]. Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 107](#), [fig. 546-547](#), [1806]: [63](#).
TL: Portugal.

- [JS] *Euchloe belemia* ab. *desertorum* Turati, 1905. Nat. Sicil. 18(2-3): [27-28](#), [pl. 2, fig. 1-3](#).
TL: Biskra (Algeria).
- [JS] *Euchloe belemia* f.[var.] *distincta* Röber, 1907. In: Seitz, Gross-Schmett. Erde(1)1: [51](#).
TL: Philippeville (=Algiers) (Algeria).
- [JS] *Euchloe belemia* f.[var.] *palaestinensis* Röber, 1907. In: Seitz, Gross-Schmett. Erde(1)1: [51](#).
TL: Palestine.
- [JS] *Euchloe belemia* f. *intermedia* Graves, 1919. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 31(4): [63](#).
TL: S Palestine.
- [JS] *Euchloe belemia* ssp. *moslemi* Speyer, 1988. Linneana Belgica 11(7): [329-332, fig.](#)
TL: Kirkuk (Iraq).
- [JS] *Euchloe belemia* ssp. *antiatlantica* Krajcik, 2015. Animma.x (64).
TL: Tafraout, Ameln (Morocco).
- [JS] *Euchloe belemia* ssp. *altamontana* TARRIER & André, 2016. Alexanor 27(6): [362-364](#).
TL: Ait-Abdallah, Djebel Akoumbi (SW Anti-Atlas, Morocco).

Euchloe falloui (Allard, 1867)

- [ORIG] *Anthocharis falloui* Allard, 1867. Ann. Soc. entomol. Fr. (4)7: [312](#), [318-319](#), [pl. 6, fig. 1a-b](#).
TL: Biskra (Algeria).
- [JS] *Euchloe seitzi* Röber, 1907. In: Seitz, Gross-Schmett. Erde (1)1: [52](#), [pl. 20 g\[1-2\]](#).
TL: Biskra (Algeria).
- [JS] *Euchloe falloui* ssp. *obsolescens* Rothschild, 1913. Novit. Zool. 20: [112](#).
TL: South Oued Mya (Algeria).
- [JS] *Euchloe falloui* ssp. *fairuzae* TARRIER, 1996. Alexanor 19(4): [195-198, fig. 1](#).
TL: Tizi-n-Tiniffitt, djebel Sarrho, Anti-Atlas oriental (Morocco).

Subgenus

Iberochloe Back, Knebelberger & Miller, 2008

- [ORIG] *Iberochloe* Back, Knebelberger & Miller, 2008. Entomol. Z. 118(4): [162-163](#).
TS: *Papilio tagis* Hübner, [1804] by original designation.
- [JS] *Phyllocharis* Schatz, [1886]. In: Staudinger & Schatz, Exot. Schmett. 2(2): [71](#).
TS: *Papilio tagis* Hübner, [1804] by monotypy ; *nec Phyllocharis* Dalman, 1824. Ephem. Entomol.: 21.

Euchloe tagis (Hübner, [1804])

- [JS] *Papilio tagis* Hübner, [1804]. Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 110, fig. 565-566](#), [1806]: [64](#).
TL: River Tagus (Portugal).
- [JS] *Pieris bellezina* Boisduval, [1828]. Eur. Lepid. Ind. Meth.1: [9](#).
TL: Provence (S France).
- [JS] *Papilio belledice* Geyer, [1832]. In: Hübner, Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 189, fig. 929-930](#).
TL: -.
- [JS] *Anthocharis tagis* f.[var.] *lusitanica* Oberthür, 1909. Ét. lépid. comp. 3: [145](#).

- TL: Portugal.
- [JS] *Anthocharis tagis* f.[var.] *alhambrae* Oberthür, 1909. Ét. lépid. comp.3: [145](#).
- TL: Granada (S Spain).
- [IFS] *Euchloë tagis bellezina* f. *gallica* Verity, [1908]. Rhop. Pal.: 183, [1909]: pl. 37, fig. 31.
- TL: Hautes-Alpes (SE France).
- [JS] *Euchloe tagis* ab. *alhambra* Ribbe, 1910. Dt. entomol. Z. Iris 23(2): [120](#).
- TL: Granada (S Spain).
- [JS] *Euchloe tagis* var. *granadensis* Ribbe, 1910. Dt. entomol. Z. Iris 23(2): [120](#).
- TL: Ronda, Granada (S Spain).
- [ND] *Euchloë tagis* race *castellana* Verity, [1911]. Rhop. Pal.: 339.
- TL: Aranjuez (prov. Madrid, C Spain) ; Nomen nudum ?
- [JS] *Euchloë tagis* race *granatae* Verity, [1911]. Rhop. Pal.: 339.
- TL: Ronda, Granada (S Spain).
- [JS] *Euchloë (Elphinstonia) tagis* ssp. *castellana* Alberti, 1945. Misc. Entomol. 42(6): [86-87, pl. 5-6, fig. 12-14](#).
- TL: Aranjuez (prov. Madrid, C Spain).
- [JS] *Euchloe tagis* ssp. *atlasica* Rungs, 1950. Bull. Soc. Sci. nat. Maroc 28: [144](#).
- TL: col de Tamrabta (Middle Atlas, Morocco).
- [JS] *Euchloe tagis* ssp. *dauidi* Torres Méndez & Verdugo Paez, 1985. SHILAP Revta. lepid. 13(50): [151-152](#).
- TL: San Roque (Cádiz prov., S Spain).
- [ND] *Euchloe tagis reisseri* Bros & Schmidt-Koehl, 1979. Mitt. entomol. Ges. Basel 29(1): [10](#).
- TL: Mt. Tisuka, Djebel Chaoun (Rif, Morocco) ; Nomen nudum.
- [JS] *Euchloe tagis* ssp. *reisseri* Back & Reissinger, 1989. Nota lepid. 12(2): [96, fig. 3](#).
- TL: Xauen [W Rif, Morocco) ; Stat. nov. for *Euchloe tagis reisseri* Bros & Schmidt-Koehl, 1979.
- [JS] *Euchloe tagis* ssp. *calvensis* Casini, 1993. Linneana Belgica 14(1): [9-11, fig.](#)
- TL: Monte Calvi (Livorno prov., Tuscany, Italy).
- [JS] *Euchloe tagis* ssp. *salazari* Fernandez-Vidal, 1996. Bol. SEA 14: [63](#).
- TL: Picos de Oulego (Orense prov., NW Spain) ; Nomen nudum ?
- [JS] *Euchloe tagis* ssp. *piemonti* Back, 2001. Atalanta 32(1/2): [100, fig.](#)
- TL: Valdieri, ... Andonno (Piemonte, NW Italy).
- [JS] *Euchloe tagis* ssp. *alhajarae* Olivares & Back, 2004. Linneana Belgica 19(5): [236-237, fig. 16-17](#).
- TL: Sierra de Aracena (Huelva prov., Spain).
- [JS] *Euchloe tagis* ssp. *aveyronensis* Maux & Carsus, 2007. Lambillionia 107: [437, fig. 1-11](#).
- TL: Saint Antonin Noble Val (Tarn-et-Garonne dep., France).
- [JS] *Euchloe (Iberochloe) tagis* ssp. *gibraltariensis* Back, 2016. Atalanta 47(1/2): [125-126, fig.](#)
- TL: Gibraltar, Upper Rock (Gibraltar, UK).
- [JS] *Euchloe (Iberochloe) tagis* ssp. *apuanica* Manil & Casini, 2021. Lépidoptères 30(78): [31, 39 fig.](#)
- TL: Monte Sagro (Massa prov., Italy).
- [JS] *Euchloe (Iberochloe) tagis* ssp. *toscanica* Manil & Casini, 2021. Lépidoptères 30(78): [31, 39, fig.](#)
- TL: Pomaia (Pisa prov., Italy).

ESU *E. pechi* (Staudinger, 1885)

[ORIG] *Anthocharis pechi* Staudinger, 1885. Entomol. Nachr. 11(1): [10-11](#).

TL: Tazoult (Algeria).

Subgenus

Elphinstonia Klots, 1930

[ORIG] *Euchloe (Elphinstonia)* Klots, 1930. Bull. Brooklyn Entomol. Soc. NS 25(2): [87](#).

TS: *Anthocharis charlonia* Donzel, 1842 by original designation.

Euchloe charlonia (Donzel, 1842)

[ORIG] *Anthocharis charlonia* Donzel 1842. Ann. Soc. entomol. Fr. 11(2): [197-198](#), [pl. 8, fig. 1](#).

TL: M'Sila (Algeria).

[JS] *Anthocharis levaillantii* Lucas, 1847. Ann. Soc. entomol. Fr.(2)5(Bull.): [xlix-l](#).

TL: Djebel-Amour (Algeria).

Euchloe penia (Freyer, [1851])

[ORIG] *Pontia penia* Freyer, [1851]. Neuere Beitr. Schmett. 6(96): [149-150](#), [pl. 574, fig. 4](#).

TL: Malatia (Turkey).

[JS] *Anthocharis charlonia* var. *mesopotamica* Baker, [1890]. Trans. Entomol. Soc. Lond. 1889: [524-525](#).

TL: Malatia (Turkey).

[JS] *Anthocharis charlonia* race *thessalica* Mezger, 1936. Lambillionea 36: [35-36](#), [63-64](#).

TL: Mount Olympus (Greece).

Euchloe bazae Fabiano, 1993

[ORIG] *Euchloe charlonia* ssp. *bazae* Fabiano, 1993. Linneana Belgica 14(4): [207-209](#), [pl. 1, fig. 1-2](#).

TL: Hoya de Baza (Granada prov., S Spain).

[JS] *Euchloe bazae* ssp. *iberae* Back, Olivares & Leestmans, 2005. Linneana Belgica 20(2): [67-72, fig. 1a-d, 2a-d](#).

TL: Caspe (Zaragoza prov., NE Spain).

Genus

Zegris Boisduval, 1836

[ORIG] *Zegris* Boisduval, 1836. Hist. Nat. Ins. Lépid.1: [552-553](#).

TS: *Papilio eupheme* Esper, [1804] by original designation.

[JS] *Microzegris* Alphéraky, 1913. In: Oberthür, Étud. Lépid. comp. 7: [232](#).

TS: *Pontia pyrothoë* Eversmann, 1832 by monotypy.

[IS] *Pyrothoia* Verity, 1929. Ann. Soc. entomol. Fr.98(3): [348](#).

TS: *Pontia pyrothoë* Eversmann, 1832 by monotypy.

Zegris pyrothoë (Eversmann, 1832)

[ORIG] *Pontia pyrothoë* Eversmann, 1832. Nouv. Mém. Soc. imp. nat. Moscou 2: [352](#), [pl. 20, fig. 3-4](#).

TL: Indersk (Kazakhstan).

Zegris eupheme (Esper, [1804])

[ORIG] *Papilio eupheme* Esper, [1804]. Schmett. Abb. Nat. Suppl. 1(1): [105-106](#), [pl. 113 \(cont. 68\)](#), [fig. 2-3](#).

TL: Sevastopol (Crimea Rep., Russian Federation).

[JS] *Pontia erothoe* Eversmann, 1832. Nouv. Mém. Soc. imp. nat. Moscou 2: [351-352](#), [pl. 20](#), [fig. 1-2](#).

TL: Chapchachi (Kharabolinsky distr., Astrakhan Prov., Russian Federation).

[JS] *Pieris menestho* Ménétries, 1832. Cat. rais. Caucase: [245](#).

TL: Talyche (Azerbaijan).

[JS] *Anthocharis eupheme* var. *tschudica* Herrich-Schäffer, [1850]. Syst. Bearb. Schmett. Eur. 1: [pl. 94](#), [fig. 449-450](#) ; 6(Nachtrag): [20](#) [1851].

TL: Kirgis steppes (NW Kazakhstan).

ESU Z. meridionalis (Lederer, 1853)

[ORIG] *Anthocharis eupheme* var. *meridionalis* Lederer, 1853. Verh. zool.-bot. Ver. Wien 2(Abhandl.): [30](#).

TL: Andalusia (S Spain).

[JS] *Zegris eupheme* ssp. *maroccana* Bernardi, 1950. Bull. Soc. entomol. Mulhouse6: 16, fig.

TL: Ifrane (Morocco).

[JS] *Zegris eupheme* ssp. *pero-mudo* Agenjo, 1963. Eos 39(3-4): [341](#), [fig. 2](#).

TL: Estépar, cuenca del río Arlanzón (Burgos prov., Spain).

Genus

Anthocharis Boisduval, Rambur & Graslin, [1833]

[ORIG] *Anthocharis* Boisduval, Rambur & Graslin, [1833]. Coll. icon. hist. Chen. Eur.: [\[31\]](#), [pl. \[Papillonides\] 5](#).

TS: *Papilio cardamines* Linnaeus, 1758 by monotypy.

[JH] *Midea* Herrich-Schäffer, 1867. Corresp.-Bl. zool.-min. Ver. Regensburg 21(9): [105](#) ; 21(11): [143](#).

TS: *Papilio genutia* Fabricius, 1793 ; nec Bruzelius, [1855]. Beskr. Hydrachn.: 35.

[JS] *Tetracharis* Grote, 1898. Proc. Amer. Phil. Soc. 37: [37](#).

TS: *Anthocharis cethura* Felder C. & Felder R., [1865] by monotypy.

[JS] *Paramidea* Kuznetsov, 1929. Lepid. Fauna U.S.S.R 1(2): 58.

TS: *Anthocharis scolymus* Butler, 1866 by original designation.

[JS] *Anthocharis (Falcapica)* Klots, 1930. Bull. Brooklyn Entomol. Soc. NS 25(2): [83](#).

TS: *Papilio genutia* Fabricius, 1793 by original designation ; Nom. nov. for *Midea* Herrich-Schäffer, 1867.

Anthocharis cardamines (Linnaeus, 1758)

[ORIG] *Papilio cardamines* Linnaeus, 1758. Syst. Nat. (ed. 10)1: [468-469](#).

TL: Sweden.

[JS] *Pontia [cardamines] turrilis* Ochseneimer, 1816. Schmett. Eur. 4: [155-156](#).

TL: Italy.

[JS] *Anthocharis cardamines cardaminoides* Brown, 1880. Naturaliste 2: [180-181](#).

- TL: Bordeaux (W France).
- [JS] *Euchloe hesperidies* Newnham, 1894. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 5(4): [97](#).
- TL: England (UK).
- [JS] *Anthocharis cardamines* var. *phoenissa* Kalchberg, 1895. Jahresber. Wien. Entomol. Ver. 5: [27-28](#).
- TL Haifa (N Israel).
- [JS] *Anthocharis cardamines* f. *speciosa* Röber, 1907. In: Seitz, Gross-Schmet. Erde (1)1: [54](#).
- TL: S Styria (Austria).
- [JS] *Euchloe cardamines britannica* Verity, [1908]. Rhopal. Pal.: 190.
- TL: Kent, Sussex, ... (UK).
- [JS] *Euchloe cardamines meridionalis* Verity, [1908]. Rhopal. Pal.: 190.
- TL: Florence (Italy).
- [JH] *Euchloe cardamines graeca* Verity, [1911]. Rhopal. Pal.: 341.
- TL: Greece ; *nec Euchloe belia [= ausonia] graeca* Verity, 1908. Rhopal. Pal.: 175.
- [JS] *Euchloe cardamines* race *montivaga* Turati & Verity, 1912. Bull. Soc. Entomol. Ital. 43: [232](#).
- TL: Terme di Valdieri (Piedmont, NW Italy).
- [JH] *Euchloe cardamines* var. *volgensis* Sheldon, 1914. Entomologist 47(617): [270](#).
- TL: Tschapurnik (Volgograd obl., Russian Federation) ; *nec Euchloe ausonia volgensis* Krulikovsky, 1897.
- [JS] *Euchloe cardamines* var. *hibernica* Williams, [1916]. Trans. Lond. Nat. Hist. Soc. 1915: [71](#).
- TL: Ireland.
- [JS] *Anthocharis cardamines* race *turritiferens* Verity, 1924. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 35(suppl.): ([16](#)).
- TL: Palermo (Sicily, S Italy).
- [JS] *Anthocharis cardamines* race *catalonica* Sagarra, 1930. Butil. Inst. Catal. Hist. Nat. 30(9): [111-112](#).
- TL: Vallvidrera (Barcelona prov., NE Spain).
- [NN] *Euchloe cardamines hellas* Hemming, 1933. Entomologist 66: 278.
Nom. nov., replacement name for *Euchloe cardamines graeca* Verity, [1911].
- [NN] *Euchloe cardamines sheldoni* Hemming, 1934. Stylops 3(5): [98](#).
Nom. nov., replacement name for *Euchloe cardamines volgensis* Sheldon, 1914.
- [JS] *Anthocharis cardamines ondrii* Kattulas & Koutsaftikis, 1976. Biol. Gallo-Hellen. 7(1-2): 154.
- TL: Kastellorizo (Rhodes Isl., Greece).
- [JS] *Anthocharis cardamines* ssp. *nevadae* Back, 2020. Guide Butt. Pal. Reg. Pieridae(4): [17](#).
- TL: Huescar (NE Granada prov., S Spain).

Anthocharis belia (Linnaeus, 1767)

- [ORIG] *Papilio belia* Linnaeus, 1767. Syst. Nat.(ed. 12) 1(2): [761](#).
- TL: Algeria.
- [JS] *Papilio eupheno* Linnaeus, 1767. Syst. Nat.(ed. 12) 1(2): [762](#).
- TL: Algeria.
- [JS] *Anthocharis douei* Pierret, 1836. Ann. Soc. Entomol. Fr. 5: [367-370](#), pl. [9A](#).
- TL: Algeria ; original spellings: *Anthocharis doucei* (p. 367) ; *Anthocharis douei* (pl. 5A).

- [JS] *Anthocharis eupheno* var. *androgynae* Leech, 1886. Proc. Zool. Soc. Lond. 1: [122-123](#).
TL: Mogador (=Essaouira, Marrakesh-Safi reg., W Morocco).
- [JS] *Anthocharis eupheno monastiriensis* Soures, 1998. Bull. Soc. Entomol. Mulhouse 54: 55.
TL: Tunisia.

***Anthocharis euphenoides* Staudinger, 1869**

- [ORIG] *Anthocharis euphenoides* Staudinger, 1869. Entomol. Ztg. 30(1-3): [92-93](#).
TL: S Europe (Spain).
- [JS] *Papilio eupheno* Esper, 1777. Schmett. Abb. Nat. 1(1): [pl. 28 \(suppl. 4\), fig. 1a-b](#) ; [1779]: [321-322](#).
TL: Marseilles (S France).
- [JS] *Euchloe calleuphenia* Butler, 1869. Entomol. Mounth. Mag. 5: [271](#).
TL: Gibraltar (S Iberian Peninsula)
- [JS] *Anthocharis euphenoides* f. *vernetensis* Oberthür, 1909. Étud. Lépid. Comp. 3: [137](#).
TL: Vernet-les-Bains (Pyrénées-Orientales dep., S France)
- [JS] *Euchloe euphenoides andalusica* Ribbe, 1910. Dt. entomol. Z. Iris 23(2): [122-123](#).
TL: Andalusia (S Spain).
- [JS] *Anthocharis euphenoides* race *alpium* Verity, 1926. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 38(12): [171-172](#).
TL: Oulx (Piedmont, NW Italy)
- [JS] *Anthocharis euphenoides italarum* Dannehl, 1929. Mitt. Munch. Entomol. Ges. 19(5-9): [98](#).
TL: Campagna,... Monte Paradiso, Majella (C Italy)
- [JS] *Anthocharis euphenoides cardaphenoides* Lorković, 1953. Physiol. Comp. Oecol. 3: 315.
TL: -.
- [ND] *Anthocharis euphenoides* ssp. *calzadillai* Gómez Bustillo & Fernández-Rubio, 1974. Marip. Peníns. Ibér. Ropal. 2: [229](#).
TL: Aranjuez (Madrid prov., C Spain) ; Nomen nudum.
- [JS] *Anthocharis belia* ssp. *calzadillai* Gómez Bustillo, 1985. SHILAP 13(49): [23](#).
TL El Regajal, Aranjuez (Madrid prov., C Spain).
- [JS] *Anthocharis* [sic] *euphenoides* ssp. *dalessandroi* Bollino, Vitale & Sala, 1996. Lambillionea 96: [33-34, fig.](#)
TL: Morano (Consenza prov., Calabria, S Italy).

***Anthocharis gruneri* Herrich-Schäffer, [1851]**

- [ORIG] *Anthocharis gruneri* Herrich-Schäffer, [1851]. Syst. Bearb. Schmett. Eur. 1: [pl. 115, fig. 551-554](#) ; 6(Nachtrag): [20](#).
TL: Crete [Error] ; Amasia (Turkey).
- [NN] *Anthocharis gruneri* Frivaldsky, [1845]. Kir. Magyar Termész. Társ. Évk. 1: [170](#).
TL: Greece ? ; *nomen nudum*.
- [JH] *Pontia gruneri* Freyer, [1851]. Neuere Beitr. Schmett. 6(96): [150, pl. 575, fig. 1-2](#).
TL: Amasia (Turkey) ; *nec* Herrich-Schäffer, [1851]: [pl. 115, fig. 551-554](#).
- [JS] *Anthocharis gruneri* var. *armeniaca* Christoph, 1893. Dt. Entomol. Z. 6(1): [86](#).
TL: Ordubad (Azerbaijan).
- [JS] *Anthocharis gruneri* var. *homogena* Heyne, 1895. In: Rühl, Pal. Grossschmett. 1: [719](#).
TL: Mesopotamia (Syria ; Iraq).

- [JS] *Anthocharis gruneri* f. *diluta* Röber, 1907. In: Seitz, Gross-Schmet. Erde (1)1: [54](#).
TL: Ankara (Turkey).
- [JS] *Anthocharis gruneri* f. *eros* Röber, 1907. In: Seitz, Gross-Schmet. Erde (1)1: [54](#).
TL: Syria.
- [JS] *Euchloe gruneri* ssp. *macedonica* Buresch, 1921. Spis. bulg. Akad. Nauk. 23: 162-163.
TL: Negortsi, Gevgelija (S North Macedonia).
- [JS] *Anthocharis gruneri* ssp. *parnassia* Bernardi, 1970. Lambillionea 70: [2-4](#).
TL: Mount Parnassus (Greece).

Anthocharis damone Boisduval, 1836

- [ORIG] *Anthocharis damone* Boisduval, 1836. Hist. Nat. Ins. Lépid. 1: [564](#).
TL: Sicily (S Italy).
- [JS] *Pontia eunomia* Freyer, [1851]. Neuere Beitr. Schmett. 6(96): [149](#), [pl. 574, fig. 3](#).
TL: ? (E Anatolia, Turkey).
- [JS] *Anthocharis damone* f. *pallida* Röber, 1907. In: Seitz, Gross-Schmet. Erde (1)1: [55](#).
TL: Mesopotamia (Iraq ?).
- [JS] *Anthocharis damone* f. *privimacula* Stauder, 1922. Mitt. Munch. Entomol. Ges. 12(1-6): [24](#).
TL: Aspromonte (Calabria, S Italy).
- [JS] *Anthocharis damone* ssp. *hollaenderi* Seyer, 1980. Mitt. Entomol. Ges. Basel NF 30(1): [1-3, fig.](#)
TL: Drim-Klisura (North Macedonia).
- [JS] *Anthocharis damone* ssp. *steinelti* Seyer, 1984. Entomol. Z. 94: 235.
TL: W Taurus (Antalya prov., Turkey).
- [JS] *Anthocharis damone* ssp. *flickeri* Seyer, 1985. Entomol. Z. 95: 21.
TL: Arastal, Kars (E Turkey).
- [JS] *Anthocharis damone* ssp. *calabra* Scalercio, Nazari and Back, 2025. In: Naderi, Back, Scalercio & Nazari, Ecol. Montenegr. 83: [80-81, fig. 4a-d](#).
TL: Balzate (Calabria, S Italy).
- [JS] *Anthocharis damone* ssp. *arachovae* Back & Nazari, 2025. In: Naderi, Back, Scalercio & Nazari, Ecol. Montenegr. 83: [82, fig. 4e-h](#).
TL: Arachova (Greece).
- [JS] *Anthocharis damone* ssp. *morea* Back & Nazari, 2025. In: Naderi, Back, Scalercio & Nazari, Ecol. Montenegr. 83: [82, fig. 4i-l](#).
TL: Taygetos (Greece).

Conclusion

This synonymic list offers a foundation for the taxonomy of Western Palearctic Pieridae.

By linking each name to its original description, it enhances transparency, accessibility, and historical accuracy. However, the list is not yet complete, and gaps remain in both hyperlinks and taxonomic data. Researchers, lepidopterists and enthusiasts are warmly invited to contribute by submitting missing hyperlinks, overlooked synonyms, or other relevant information.

Author contribution

Michel Taymans: conceptualisation, analysis, visualisation, writing - original draft, writing – review and editing.

Sylvain Cuvelier: analysis, validation, visualisation, writing – review and editing.

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